

AN ANALYSIS OF ITALIAN UNIVERSITY-SET CORE FACILITIES

Executive Master in Management of
Research Infrastructures, EMMRI
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Maddalena Donzelli
Università degli Studi di Milano - Statale
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INTRODUCTION

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

Europe and its Member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC) have a strong history in the field of Research Infrastructures (RI). Since the establishment of CERN in 1952, the European Union (EU) has developed a number of individual Research Infrastructures that demonstrated to be efficient practices of scientific cooperation and collaboration, and major strategic investments to support innovation, technological advances and global competitiveness of the European Research Area (ERA).

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) was established in 2002 with a mandate of the EU Council to support the development of a coherent and strategy-led approach to policy-making on Research Infrastructures in Europe, and to facilitate multilateral initiatives leading to the exploitation and implementation of Research Infrastructures, at European and international level. ESFRI's delegates – nominated by the Research Ministers of the MS/AC and including a representative of the European Commission (EC) – are working together to develop a joint vision and a common strategy. This strategy aims at overcoming the limits due to fragmentation of individual policies, and provides Europe with the most up-to-date Research Infrastructures, responding to the rapidly evolving science frontiers, advancing also the knowledge-based technologies and their extended use to create solutions to tackle global societal challenges.

The definition of **Research Infrastructure** has expanded broadly from large-scale plants for physics-based machines to any centre of knowledge or facility which is core to a particular research discipline, such as a database or museum, as well as distributed RIs operating at multiple sites.

Its concept is quite unique and clearly outlined at European level. In Article 2 (6) of the Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of 11 December 2013 – Establishing Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)¹ – the following definition applies.

“Research Infrastructures are facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. They include major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives and scientific data, e-infrastructure, such as data and computing systems and communication networks and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation. Such infrastructures may be 'single-sited', 'virtual' or 'distributed'”.

This definition has been recalled in the ESFRI Roadmap 2018² and further developed to better define the organization models for *single-sited* and *distributed* RIs.

“[...] RIs are implemented with different organisation models: single-sited Research Infrastructures – namely large research plants in a single or a few fully dedicated sites as astronomy and astrophysics telescopes, accelerator based sources, nuclear reactor sources, extreme laser sources; or distributed Research Infrastructures – e.g. networks of observatories of the earth, oceans, biodiversity; multiple operational sites in the health and food domain; surveys and longitudinal studies of the European

¹ Establishing Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020). Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of 11 December 2013

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/legal_basis/fp/h2020-eu-estabact_en.pdf

² ESFRI Roadmap 2018

<http://roadmap2018.esfri.eu>

population; collections of physical or digital information; innovation in heritage and culture; very large computational resources. In all cases, RIs offer physical access to the researchers and/or remote use”.

In general, *single-sited RIs* are central facilities geographically localised in a single site or in a few dedicated complementary sites designed for user access, whose governance is European or international; a *distributed RI* consists of a Central Hub and interlinked National Nodes that may be absorbed partially by the distributed RI while maintaining their national or institutional programmes (i.e. National Strategy Plan) but the capacity and amount of resources engaged in the RI must be coordinated and managed centrally according to agreed statutes and common rules and procedures of the legal RI consortium (e.g. European Research Infrastructure Consortium, ERIC; Association internationale sans but lucrative, AISBL).

ESFRI has defined objectives that a Research Infrastructure – whether it is *single-sited* or *distributed* – must fulfill – since its Concept and Design towards Operation – to become a fully-fledged RI. Adopting the Lifecycle Approach, the analysis is covering the following features adapted to the type of RI and its stage of development. Notably, these overall characteristics mark the difference between a Research Infrastructure and a coordinated research network, typically international collaborations of fully independent Research Performing Organizations (RPO) (**Table 1**).

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FEATURES
Governance structure with clear responsibility and reporting lines
Legal status or legally binding attributions of coordination competences and resources (at Central Hub if distributed)
International supervisory and relevant external advisory bodies
Access policy and single access point for external users
User programme absorbing a considerable fraction of the total RI capacity
User support structure to optimise access to the relevant site, such as users office, ancillary laboratories, accommodation arrangements and logistics
Data management system providing metadata and data storage, retrieval tools and on-line/in situ/remote data reduction and analysis
Key Performance Indicators (KPI) addressing both excellence of scientific services and sustainability
Human resources policy adequate to guarantee the necessary competences for its operation (at Central hub if distributed), users programme, education and training by equal opportunity hiring and secondments
Joint investment strategy aimed at strengthening the RI through the Nodes and the common/shared facilities

Table 1. Features of European Research Infrastructures.

Since 2014, ESFRI has refined its methodology for the selection of new projects and monitoring of existing ones, and provided updated versions of the Roadmap of RIs. The last edition – published in December 2021³ – includes 21 ESFRI Projects, which are new Research Infrastructures in progress towards implementation, and 41 ESFRI Landmarks, successfully implemented Research Infrastructures. Some of the ESFRI Landmarks are also Research Infrastructures of global interest as

³ ESFRI Roadmap 2021
<https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu>

indicated by the Group of Senior Officials (GSO)⁴ on Global Research Infrastructures (GRI) in their progress reports to G7 Science ministers in 2015 (Berlin)⁵ and 2017 (Torino)⁶.

The European Commission has provided over years increasing financial support for the development and implementation of RIs of various sizes ranging from large-scale, single-sited facilities and distributed infrastructures of pan-European relevance to mid-size national facilities. This has been realised by offering dedicated funding opportunities under the EU Research Framework Programmes and the European Regional Development Funds (ERDF), since the 2nd Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development (FP2), when the concept of Transnational Access (TA) was first introduced. Major investments were provided under FP6, FP7 and FP8 (H2020) that, in addition to TA, introduced new actions including Networking Activities (NA) and Joint Research Activities (JRA), forming the Integrated Infrastructures Initiatives (I3), aiming at improving the quality of access offered in a field⁷. As Horizon Europe started, further funding opportunities for Research Infrastructures have been planned, including specific measures adopted for the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)⁸.

National investments are also crucial to support different RI types and different stages of RI development. National roadmaps alignment and harmonization of efforts from Member States, Associated Countries and the European Commission is needed to optimize the implementation and construction process of pan-European RIs.

CORE FACILITIES

A general definition of **Core Facilities** may be adapted from “Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs): Core Facilities” at National Institute of Health⁹:

“Core facilities are centralized shared research resources that provide access to instruments, technologies, services, as well as expert consultation and other services to scientific and clinical investigators. Institutions establish core facilities, including the corresponding costing structure of the facility, to provide required services to users generally with all or a portion of the cost of these services charged to users' accounts. The typical core facility is a discrete unit within an institution and may have dedicated personnel, equipment, and space for operations. In general, core facilities recover their cost, or a portion of their cost, of providing service in the form of user fees that are charged to an investigator's funds.”

It's not a case that the definition is coming from the National Institute of Health in the United States, where the concept of Core Facility had germinated more than 40 years ago. The idea developed from a milestone funding programme: the Shared Instrument Grant. This infusion of funding for shared

⁴ Group of Senior Official (GSO)

<http://www.gsogri.org/>

⁵ GSO Progress Report, Berlin 2015

http://www.gsogri.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/gso_progress_report_2015_final.pdf

⁶ GSO Progress Report, Torino 2017

http://www.gsogri.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/gso_progress_report_2017.pdf

⁷ Supporting the Transformative Impact of Research Infrastructures on European Research. HLEG Report 2020

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/strategy_on_research_and_innovation/documents/ec_rtd_transformative-impact-ris-on-euro-research.pdf

⁸ Horizon Europe: Research infrastructures

https://rea.ec.europa.eu/funding-and-grants/horizon-europe-research-infrastructure_it

⁹ Adapted from “Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs): Core Facilities”, National Institutes of Health

<https://grants.nih.gov/faqs/core-facilities.htm?anchor=question53273>

resources at research laboratories was exactly what was needed for the technologies and the instruments to be developed at NIH. The first was the automated DNA synthesizer that increased the capacity to synthesise DNA molecules thus accelerating production of reagents and save time for an increasing number of investigators¹⁰. Since the automation was providing services and products that far exceeded what most laboratories needed, the step further was to offer those services to other investigators, creating a collaborating environment for the benefit of inside and outside researchers. The common desire of sharing of protocols and challenges of people leading Core Facilities, paved the way for the establishment of the Association of Biomolecular Resource Facilities (ABRF). Currently, ABRF is a unique membership association comprising over 1,500 professional workers at research cores, representing over 340 laboratories and administrative offices in government, academia, research, industry and commercial settings¹¹.

There are five features of *Core Facilities* that differentiate them from traditional Research Laboratories¹² (Table 2).

CORE FACILITIES FEATURES

Management

Most research cores are established through high-level decision-makers at their institutions. They are often managed centrally by the office of research and receive oversight from the senior research officer, a structure necessitated by multiple factors including economic constraints, increasing research costs, and the need to maximize the value and accessibility of research facilities. Every year, managers of research cores submit a detailed report that includes key financial metrics to the office of research. This distinguishes them from most research labs that are managed discretely by their principal investigators, sometimes under departmental supervision (see Figure 1).

Expertise

Compared to traditional research labs that rely on graduate students and technicians, Core Facilities normally recruit managers and technical staff with PhD training to provide highly specialized services to a wide community of researchers.

Instrumentation

Core Facilities contain advanced equipment such as NMR and cryo-EM for shared use across an academic department, academic institution, or beyond, that are financially difficult if not impossible for individual investigators to obtain and maintain, as opposed to essential instruments for day-to-day research in traditional research labs.

User

Sharing is the central feature of all research cores. In many places, they are also called “shared core facilities,” a name that highlights their accessibility to researchers across different academic departments, schools, and sometimes even institutions. This is opposed to traditional labs that are normally exclusively used by people affiliated with one research group or department.

Fee

Most research cores operate under the fee-for-service model, which means users are charged service fees based on instrument service time and other services provided. A multi-tier rate structure is adopted, which charges external users (especially those from for-profit sectors) more than internal university users. A substantial share of these fees is paid at the discretion of researchers, ultimately derived by their research grant funding.

Table 2. Features of Core Facilities.

¹⁰ Ronald L. Niece. Journey to Now: The Origins of ABRF. *Journal of Biomolecular Techniques* 30:32–35 © 2019 ABRF

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6693439/pdf/jbt.30-32.pdf>

¹¹ Association of Biomolecular Resource Facilities (ABRF)

<https://www.abrf.org>

¹² Yuzhou Bai & Roger C. Schonfeld. What Is a Research Core? A Primer on a Critical Component of the Research Enterprise (2021)

<https://sr.ithaka.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/SR-Report-What-Is-A-Research-Core-120621.pdf>

A schematic representation of the organisation and management structure at Core Facilities compared to a Research Laboratory is depicted in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Core Facility versus Research Laboratory.

This figure depicts that while Research Laboratories are managed discretely by their Principal Investigators, sometimes under Department supervision, Research Cores are managed by Core Managers who are coordinated centrally by the Office of Research and receive oversight from the Senior Research Officer.

There is an increasing tendency to use the definition of ‘Research Infrastructures’ to indicate any collaborative space for shared resources to support the scientific communities. Thus, RIs can be classified into three levels, according to their scope and degree of international presence and engagement.

The advanced level is represented by European Research Infrastructures (i.e. ESFRI Roadmap on RIs) as well as Research Infrastructures of national relevance which are listed on National Strategy Plans (i.e. National Roadmaps on RIs) and which are connected, or have a strong position to connect, with pan-European facilities and willing to become part of one of the ESFRI RIs in the long-term.

At the basal level, there is a myriad of Research Infrastructures developed at Universities or Research Performing Organisation and representing ‘Equipment Laboratory’ or ‘Core Facilities’. These include Department level facilities, cross-Departmental Research Infrastructures as well as Research Infrastructures which were labelled as Strategic Infrastructures (middle level). The terms ‘Research Infrastructure’ have been intentionally kept for each category to underly their intent to strategically positioning themselves for the future (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Academic Research Laboratory evolution to European Research Infrastructure.

In the higher education context, Research Cores are playing a crucial role in supporting colleagues at universities and research centers to perform cutting-edge research, to trainee faculty members and personnel staff, and to secure external funding. Their development towards a more strategic position will be essential to place them at the core of the research enterprise.

United States, for examples, have a long history in setting research cores at universities and research centres dating back to 2000. Groundbreaking biomedical research requires access to cutting edge scientific resources; however such resources are often invisible beyond the laboratories or universities where they were developed. An interesting example of ‘multi-user research facilities’ is provided by those initiatives supported by the National Science Foundation (NSF) and involving a number of Universities.

The National Science Foundation (NSF) investments provide state-of-the-art tools for research and education. These include major multi-user research facilities such as instrumentation networks, observatories, accelerators, detectors, telescopes, research vessels, aircraft, and simulators. In addition, investments in cyber-enabled and geographically distributed user facilities are increasing as a result of rapid advances in computer, information, and communication technologies. NSF’s investments are coordinated with those of other organizations, federal agencies, and international partners to ensure they are complementary and well-integrated. Planning, operations, and maintenance of major multi-user facilities are funded through the Research and Related Activities (R&RA) account, with most construction funded through the Major Research Equipment and Facilities Construction (MREFC) account¹³.

¹³ Major Multi-User Research Facilities Funding
https://www.nsf.gov/about/budget/fy2018/pdf/36_fy2018.pdf

THE ITALIAN LANDSCAPE

The European Commission and ESFRI encourage Member States and Associated Countries to develop their own National Roadmaps on Research Infrastructures by adopting the ESFRI methodology and approach. The National Roadmaps are indeed relevant plans which enable MS/AC to identify national priorities and support their funding both at national and European level. This alignment throughout Europe will prompt the harmonisation of the process towards the implementation of new and upgraded RIs and help developing a consistent and coherent ecosystem of Research Infrastructures, which implies reinforcing European RI policy and international cooperation as well as connecting with the educational system.

The Italian government has responded to this invitation and has developed a strategic approach to identify national priorities as outlined in the Decree of the Italian Minister of University and Research (MUR) adopting the National Research Infrastructure Plan 2021-2027 (PNIR)¹⁴ as an integral part of the National Research Program 2021-2027 (PNR) and including the annex National Plan for Open Science¹⁵.

The National Research Infrastructure strategy plan embraces the methodology elaborated by the European Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) to guarantee that Europe is equipped with world-class Research Infrastructures enabling the scientific communities to perform cutting-edge research in every domain and sector. This European landscape of RIs will foster scientific excellence and promote innovation to achieve the most challenging objectives undertaken at European and global level.

Based on ESFRI criteria and national priority areas for research and innovation – in line with agenda priorities and related objectives set in the new European Research Area – the plan provides a map of the Italian landscape of Research Infrastructures of national and also regional interest: a total of about 200 initiatives identified by public research bodies (Enti Pubblici di Ricerca, EPR), Universities and Regions as Research Infrastructures (RI) or, in some cases, Technological & Innovation Infrastructures (TI).

The majority concern high-priority RIs (74): existing RIs (e.g. ERICs) or to be implemented RIs (e.g. EUPRAXIA) mainly in the European and international context and to which Italy already provides political and financial support (e.g. by corresponding the Fondo Ordinario degli Enti Pubblici di Ricerca, FOE); existing RIs (e.g. NFFA) or to be implemented RIs (e.g. EuroNanoLab) that represent new opportunities for investments. There is also a consistent number of mid-priority RIs (35) – some of which are already present at European and international level (e.g. CUSBO) – that represent also new opportunities for investments. The minority group (22) consists of low-priority proposals for new projects as potential new investments. Furthermore, there is a political and economic commitment of the Regions in supporting local initiatives with potential national and international development. Some are university-set initiatives that operate as academic Core Facilities of in-house and regional relevance and that shall be interested in adopting principles and models that provide them the opportunity to implement performance and to compete at national level for new coming funding opportunities.

¹⁴ Piano Nazionale Infrastrutture di Ricerca (PNIR) 2021 – 2027

<https://www.mur.gov.it/sites/default/files/2021-10/Decreto%20Ministeriale%20n.1082%20del%2010-09-2021%20-%20PNIR%202021%20-%202027.pdf>

¹⁵ Programma Nazionale per la ricerca 2021-2027

<https://www.mur.gov.it/sites/default/files/2021-01/Pnr2021-27.pdf>

The Italian Government through the MUR felt the urgency to inject new resources into the RI ecosystem to set the conditions for medium to long-term development of RIs, an important element of competitiveness of national and European research, and thus provided measures to tackle this challenge. In December 2021, two calls for proposals of new Research Infrastructures and Technological & Innovation Infrastructures have been published on the website of the Ministry of University and Research. The investment consists of € 1.58 billion coming from the supply resources offered by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR)¹⁶.

With a capability of € 1.08 billion, MUR intends to finance at least 20 Research Infrastructures – i.e. large plants, resources and related services used by the scientific community to carry out excellent research in several disciplines to perform frontier research¹⁷. The expected distribution of the budget to the six ESFRI thematic domains is the following: € 400 million to Physical Sciences and Engineering (PSE), € 200 million to Environment (ENV) and Health & Food (H&F), € 100 million to Social & Cultural Innovation (SCI), € 90 million to Data, Computing and Digital Research Infrastructures (DIGIT) and Energy (ENE). The remaining € 500 million investment are allocated to create or update at least 10 Technological & Innovation Infrastructures with the aim of promoting close integration between research and industry to foster their innovation potential and accelerate country's economic growth¹⁸.

The invitation to participate to the call was addressed to leaders of high- and mid-priority Research Infrastructures identified in the PNIR to present proposals in one of the three different lines of action: i) the enhancement of high-priority RIs; ii) the creation of new high- and mid-priority RIs; iii) or the creation of thematic / multidisciplinary networks of high- and mid-priority RIs.

Consortia of EPRs and Universities submitted thirty-nine proposals of RIs for a total request of contribution of € 1.8 billion (out of the budgeted € 1.08 billion) by the deadline of 28th February. A competitive and peer-review evaluation is currently ongoing by means of dedicated Panels consisting of international scientific experts in the relative field. New projects that deserve to be financed will thus be selected to enter the negotiation phase, and individual grant agreements will be signed by the current summer.

This injection of resources will change the landscape of RIs including those university-set initiatives that operate as academic Core Facilities of in-house and regional relevance (e.g. UNITECH at University of Milano). Their role will become important according to their ability to implement towards standard models, or engaging with the existing RIs as suppliers of some service/competence and become beneficiary of specific funding at national and European level.

A good representation of this model is the Nanoscience Foundries And Fine Analysis (NFFA) developed from the early stages in 2008 starting out with the NFFA-Design Study (INFRAIA, Integrating and opening existing national and regional research infrastructures of European interest), up to the latest H2020 project NFFA-Europe Pilot (NEP) launched in March 2021. The project, coordinated by the Istituto Officina dei Materiali of the National Research Council (CNR-IOM), involves twenty-two

¹⁶ PNRR calls for Research Infrastructures and Technological & Innovation Infrastructures

<https://www.mur.gov.it/it/news/mercoledi-29122021/pnrr-pubblicati-i-bandi-le-infrastrutture-di-ricerca-e-le-infrastrutture>

¹⁷ Avviso pubblico per la presentazione di proposte progettuali per “Rafforzamento e creazione di Infrastrutture di Ricerca” da finanziare nell’ambito del PNRR. Avviso n. 3264 del 28-12-2021

<https://www.mur.gov.it/it/atti-e-normativa/avviso-n-3264-del-28-12-2021>

¹⁸ Avviso per la concessione di finanziamenti destinati alla realizzazione o ammodernamento di Infrastrutture tecnologiche di innovazione. Avviso n. 3265 del 28-12-2021

<https://www.mur.gov.it/it/atti-e-normativa/avviso-n-3265-del-28-12-2021>

partners from nine Member States – France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and Austria – and from Switzerland, and aims at increasing European competitiveness in nanosciences and nanotechnologies. Among the beneficiaries, some are set at universities: the Condensed Matter Physics Theoretical group that has a significant track record in the field of Theoretical Spectroscopy and the Molecular beams and nano-crystalline Materials laboratory (LGM, belonging to the Interdisciplinary Centre for Nano-structured Materials and Interfaces – CIMaINa) both sited at the Physics Department of the University of Milano.

Another example is provided by the EU-funded LaserLab-Europe project (INFRAIA, Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities), the European consortium of major national laser research infrastructures, covering advanced laser science and applications in most domains of research and technology, with particular emphasis on areas with high industrial and social impact, such as bio- and nanophotonics, material analyses, biology and medicine. Among the XX partners, the Centre for Ultrafast Science and Biomedical Optics (CUSBO) is set at the Physics Department of the Politecnico of Milano.

Both projects are cited in the PNIR: NFFA as RI of European interest and high priority, CUSBO of regional and national interest of mid priority.

ANALYSIS OF ITALIAN CORE FACILITIES

PURPOSE AND FOCUS

The aim of this study is to develop a comprehensive and common tool for the analysis of Core Facilities established at Italian Universities, and suggest good practices for identifying scientific relevance, governing and management structure, funding opportunities, access rules, running costs, dedicated human resources and data management.

It is motivated by the need to identify priorities and to develop a strategic approach for strengthening the national research ecosystem as defined in the PNIR, the National Research Infrastructure Plan 2021-2027. Among these, some are university-set initiatives that operate as academic Core Facilities of in-house and regional relevance and that shall be interested in adopting principles and models that provide them the opportunity to implement performance and to compete at national level for new coming funding opportunities.

Clear definitions and comparison analysis will in turn help developing models to establish success stories that will bring new resources into the national research and innovation system.

RESOURCES AND METHODOLOGY

The list of Research Infrastructures of national and regional interest is provided by the Italian Roadmap on RIS¹⁴ updated in October 2021 and that serves also as reference for the ongoing selection of new projects of Research Infrastructure¹⁶. On the other hand, a survey of existing academic Core Facilities and Research Infrastructures embedded in Universities is not available.

The Working Group (WG) set at the University of Milano-Statale was mandated to address the need for an overview of existing university-lead CFs at the national level. Indeed, the need of an inventory of existing CFs is a prerequisite for policy-making as well as for specific actions directed at their implementation.

National Core Facilities and Research Infrastructures identification

To tackle this challenge, the WG set out a classification analysis of existing Core Facilities in the Italian landscape by addressing the following series of queries.

QUESTION	SEARCH
Which is a University-set Core Facility?	WEB
Which is a University-set Core Facility in the Core Facility Network?	NETWORK
Which is a University-set Core Facility labelled as Research Infrastructure of (at least) regional interest?	PNIR

First, the WG performed a web search with the name 'Core Facility' looking for initiatives at public Universities on the Italian territory that fulfil the following definition adapted from "*Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs): Core Facilities*" at National Institute of Health⁹:

“Core facilities are centralized shared research resources that provide access to instruments, technologies, services, as well as expert consultation and other services to scientific and clinical investigators. Institutions establish core facilities, including the corresponding costing structure of the facility, to provide required services to users generally with all or a portion of the cost of these services charged to users' accounts. The typical core facility is a discrete unit within an institution and may have dedicated personnel, equipment, and space for operations. In general, core facilities recover their cost, or a portion of their cost, of providing service in the form of user fees that are charged to an investigator's funds.”

The web-search scores some initiatives that were further verified by cross-checking their participation to the Italian Network of Core Facilities promoted by the University of Trento.

QUESTION	SEARCH
Which is a University-set Core Facility?	WEB
Which is a University-set Core Facility in the Core Facility Network?	NETWORK
Which is a University-set Core Facility labelled as Research Infrastructure of (at least) regional interest?	PNIR

In parallel, the WG conducted an analysis by searching for university-lead Research Infrastructures of ‘regional interest’ (RI-R) among those identified by the consultation on regional priorities and reported on Table 7 of the PNIR. Those indicated with the asterisk also belong to the list of RIs of ‘national interest’ (RI-N) described in Table 5 of PNIR.

QUESTION	SEARCH
Which is a University-set Core Facility?	WEB
Which is a University-set Core Facility in the Core Facility Network?	NETWORK
Which is a University-set Core Facility labelled as Research Infrastructure of (at least) regional interest?	PNIR

The combination of the two analyses provided the **Table 3** where the RIs of interest at university level are classified according to regional location, web search, CF Network participation and PNIR indication. Only some entries originated from both analysis whether most are uniquely identified from one search only.

REGION	UNIVERSITY	WEB SEARCH	NETWORK	PNIR	ACRONYM
SICILIA	UniPA	X		RI-R	ATeN
PIEMONTE	UniPO	X	X	RI-R	CAAD
ABRUZZO	UniCH	X	X		CAST
VENETO	UniVE	X		RI-R RI-N	CeTrA
LOMBARDIA	UniPV	X	X	RI-R	CGS

PA TRENTO	UniTN	X	X		CIBIO
TOSCANA	UniPI	X	X	RI-R	CISUP
VENETO	UniVR	X	X	RI-R	CPT
EMILIA-ROMAGNA	UniBO	X	X		CRBA
LOMBARDIA	PoliMI	X		RI-R	PoliFAB
CALABRIA	UniCAL	X		RI-R RI-N	STAR 2.0
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X		UNITECH COSPECT
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X		UNITECH INDACO
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X	RI-R	UNITECH NOLIMITS
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X	RI-R	UNITECH OMICs

Table 3. Identification of Core Facilities and Research Infrastructures of regional and national interest within Italian universities.

Among this selection of initiatives, the WG examined in depth those for which public information was available – e.g from the website and Core Facility official ‘*Rules and Guidelines*’– and whose reference contact people were available for further investigation and interviews.

National Core Facilities and Research Infrastructures features

The WG identified a number of aspects of CFs that might provide a common reference basis for in depth analysis of CF/RIs.

In **Table 4**, the WG prepared a list of the features and type of information that apply to CFs. Some metrics had been identified but most information is retrieved as qualitative. Most of the features meet the benchmarks used for the identification of priority projects at national level¹⁴, a process built on the criteria used for evaluation and selection of new projects of RI at European level¹⁹.

CATEGORY	INFORMATION	METRICS & MEASURABLE	DESCRIPTION
DESCRIPTION AND POSITIONING	Overview and lifecycle	Provide an overview and progress to operations	Overview and the lifecycle phase are useful to frame the the national landscape.
	Mission, Vision, Values	Provide mission statement and objectives	The mission, vision, and values are useful to frame the strategic position in the national landscape.
	Stakeholder communities	Identify and analyse stakeholders and their interests	The analysis of the Stakeholders communities helps adopting more strategic direction to foster engagement.
	Thematic research	Provide field of research	The thematic research area and interconnections with other domains also frame the position in the national landscape and allow to identify emerging research needs in the field.

¹⁹ ESFRI Roadmap 2021 Guide
https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/ESFRI_Roadmap2021_Public_Guide.pdf

GOVERNANCE & MANAGEMENT	Governing bodies with clear reporting lines	Provide a Regulation/Statutes with profile of governing bodies and their duties	Governing bodies with clear responsibility and reporting lines are critical for the success of any enterprise. They shape the very operation of the undertaking – decision-making and implementation processes, coordination of competences and resources, and the relationships amongst the various interested parties. External advisory bodies are also relevant.
	Human resources management	List of human resources and responsibilities	A Human resources policy must be in place to guarantee the necessary competences for operation, users programme, education and training by equal opportunity hiring and secondments.
	Financial Management	Identify unique responsibility for administrative management	
ACCESS PROGRAMME	User and Access policy	Describe the access rules, procedure and policy	
	Data policy	Describe the data management plan	
RESOURCES AND FUNDING	Financial Resources	Identify financial resources	Apply a joint investment strategy aimed at strengthening the common/shared facilities.
	Financial Sustainability	Check the number of EU-funded projects, European Structural Funds (ESI), National resources (FOE), Additional resources, Regional resources	A funding strategy is also needed to function as a tool that science governance actors can use to steer research. The sustainability is also an issue.
IMPACT	Education and training	Identify lecture courses, laboratory courses, seminars, presentations	
	Research	List of publications List of grants	
	Technology development	List of patents, inventions List of instrumentation and software developed	

Table 4. identification of categories and type of information to be gathered for selected Core Facilities and Research Infrastructures of regional and national interest within Italian universities.

We then developed a profile card for each CF/RI and filled it with the accessible information, mainly recovered from the *'Rules and Guidelines'* of the entity, if available. Once completed, the profile card was shared with the contact person to further refine the information. The cards were filled for thirteen out of fifteen CF/RI.

DESCRIPTION AND POSITIONING

The following **Table 5** is providing the list of the selected fifteen Case Studies.

REGION	UNIVERSITY	WEB	NETWORK	PNIR	ACRONYM	NAME	TYPE	STRUCTURE
SICILIA	UniPA	X		RI-R	ATeN	Advanced Technologies Network Center	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
PIEMONTE	UniPO	X	X	RI-R	CAAD	Centro di Ricerca Traslazionale sulle Malattie Autoimmuni e Allergiche	Research Centre	Inter-Departmental
ABRUZZO	UniCH	X	X		CAST	Center for Advanced Studies and Technology	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
VENETO	UniVE	X		RI-R RI-N	CeTra	Centre for Trace Analysis	Research Centre	Extra-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	UniPV	X	X	RI-R	CGS	Centro Grandi Strumenti	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
PA TRENTO	UniTN	X	X		CIBIO	Cellular, Computational and Integrative Biology	Core Facility	Intra-Departmental
TOSCANA	UniPI	X	X	RI-R	CISUP	Centre for Instrument Sharing	Research Centre	Inter-Departmental
VENETO	UniVR	X	X	RI-R	CPT	Centro Piattaforma Tecnologiche	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
EMILIA-ROMAGNA	UniBO	X	X		CRBA	Centro di Ricerca Biomedica Applicata	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	PoliMI	X		RI-R	Polifab	Micro-fabrication Facility	Research Facility	
CALABRIA	UniCAL	X		RI-R RI-N	STAR 2.0	Southern Europe Thomson Backscattering Source for Applied Research	Research Infrastructure	
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X		UNITECH CONSPeCT	Comprehensive Substances characterization via advanced sPecTroscopy	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X		UNITECH INDACO	Infrastruttura di Calcolo per Analisi di DATi COmplessi	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X	RI-R	UNITECH NOLIMITS	NOvel Live biolmaging Milano citTà Studi	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X	RI-R	UNITECH OMICS	Metabolomics and lipidomics, Proteomics and Peptidomics	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental

Table 5. Selected Core Facilities and Research Infrastructures within Italian universities.

Six out of fifteen CFs fulfill all three requirements and can be defined as university-set Core Facilities participating to the Italian Network of Core Facilities and indicated as Research Infrastructure of (at least) regional interest.

REGION	UNIVERSITY	WEB	NETWORK	PNIR	ACRONYM	NAME	TYPE	STRUCTURE
PIEMONTE	UniPO	X	X	RI-R	CAAD	Centro di Ricerca Traslazionale sulle Malattie Autoimmuni e Allergiche	Research Centre	Inter-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	UniPV	X	X	RI-R	CGS	Centro Grandi Strumenti	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
TOSCANA	UniPI	X	X	RI-R	CISUP	Centre for Instrument Sharing	Research Centre	Inter-Departmental
VENETO	UniVR	X	X	RI-R	CPT	Centro Piattaforma Tecnologiche	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X	RI-R	UNITECH NOLIMITS	NOvel Live biolmaging Milano clTà Studi	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X	RI-R	UNITECH OMICs	Metabolomics and lipidomics, Proteomics and Peptidomics	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental

Five out of fifteen CFs fulfill only two of the requirements and can be defined as university-set Core Facilities participating to the Italian Network of Core Facilities.

REGION	UNIVERSITY	WEB	NETWORK	PNIR	ACRONYM	NAME	TYPE	STRUCTURE
ABRUZZO	UniCH	X	X		CAST	Center for Advanced Studies and Technology	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
PA TRENTO	UniTN	X	X		CIBIO	Cellular, Computational and Integrative Biology	Core Facility	Intra-Departmental
EMILIA-ROMAGNA	UniBO	X	X		CRBA	Centro di Ricerca Biomedica Applicata	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X		UNITECH COSPECT	COmprehensive Substances characterization via advanced sPECTroscopy	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	X	X		UNITECH INDACO	INfrastruttura di Calcolo per Analisi di DATi COmplessi	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental

The remaining four fulfill two requirements and can be defined as university-set Core Facilities and indicated as Research Infrastructure of (at least) regional interest.

REGION	UNIVERSITY	WEB	NETWORK	PNIR	ACRONYM	NAME	TYPE	STRUCTURE
SICILIA	UniPA	X		RI-R	ATeN	Advanced Technologies Network Center	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental
VENETO	UniVE	X		RI-R RI-N	CeTrA	Centre for Trace Analysis	Research Centre	Extra-Departmental
LOMBARDIA	PoliMI	X		RI-R	PolifAB	Micro-fabrication Facility	Research Facility	
CALABRIA	UniCAL	X		RI-R RI-N	STAR 2.0	Southern Europe Thomson Backscattering Source for Applied Research	Research Infrastructure	

The selected fifteen Case Studies have been further classified by relevant categories of features (type, structure, evolution and lifecycle, mission, objectives, stakeholders) and analysed for their performance in terms of scientific excellence, governance and management, funding, and impact.

Most Case Studies are organised as ‘Service Centre’ or ‘Research Platform’ thus underlying their commitment to provide shared resources and services to support research. Their structure is most frequently ‘Inter-Departmental’ being promoted by several Departments of the same university who also conducts the CF activities (**Table 5**, and **Annex 1** for details of affiliation). In one case, the CF entirely depends on one only Department (i.e. CIBIO at University of Trento), while in another case researchers can join the CF by individual application (i.e. CISUP at University of Pisa). CeTrA is an exception being promoted by and engaged with intramural and extramural Departments of different institutions: Ca’ Foscari University (UniVE) and National Research Council (CNR).

The majority of identified Core Facilities are established at Universities seated in North Italy, as shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. National geographical coverage of selected Core Facilities.

Overview and Lifecycle

The evolution in time of Research Infrastructures – e.g. ESFRI Projects and Landmarks, ERICs, AISBL, Integration Actions, EU-funded Pilots, National/Regional RIs, Networks – is understood as a sequence of phases from the Concept development to long-term Operation and, eventually, Termination.

The *Lifecycle* Approach has been adopted first by the Group of Senior Officials of G7+N (GSO) and reported in the GSO Progress Report 2017²⁰ presented to the G7 Science Ministerial meeting in Torino. Subsequently, it was developed in the ESFRI Roadmap 2018²¹ and further rationalised in the HLEG Report 2020²². It's a useful instrument that helps understanding the needs and targets for managing the RI towards its implementation, as well as identifying opportunities and risks for investing in such an enterprise.

The *Lifecycle* of a RI can typically be divided into six consecutive phases: Concept, Design, Preparation, Implementation/Construction, Operation and Termination Phase Each phase is demanding for specific goals related to the scientific case and implementation case to be achieved for the sake of the initiative (see **BOX 1** for ESFRI lifecycle definitions).

The **CONCEPT** of a new RI typically emerges bottom-up from the scientific communities clustering around well-identified scientific needs and goals.

The **DESIGN** covers the proof of the scientific concept and technical feasibility of the RI, the analysis of the potential user community – both science and Innovation oriented; the outline of a business case and the rationale for the international consortium.

The **PREPARATION** – carried out at institutional, national, European or international level – is directed towards developing the RI as a fully-fledged organization.

The **IMPLEMENTATION** is different for single-sited and distributed RIs. In the first case it corresponds to an intense investment period of several years for construction engaging human and financial resources with big impact on the market – suppliers of goods and technologies. In case of distributed RIs, the implementation implies intense negotiations as both the Central Hub and the national nodes require specific commitments.

During their **OPERATION**, RIs produce frontier research and deliver advanced services for excellent science satisfying the users' demand, boosting brain circulation of early career scientists and trainees, therefore improving the ranking of their academic and research institutions.

The **TERMINATION** may encompass dissolution of the organisation, dismantling of facilities and related safety aspects and resurrection of the original site but it does not apply in these identical terms in all research domains.

BOX 1. Summary of ESFRI Lifecycle definitions.

The Concept of a Research Infrastructure is a bottom-up process emerging from scientific and technological needs of specific research communities to respond to a scientific issue or societal challenge. Once the concept of the RI is developed by the consortium of partners, the Design Phase will provide evidence for the feasibility of the RI, the basis to outline the Preparation Phase which

²⁰ GSO Progress Report 2017

http://www.gsogri.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/gso_progress_report_2017.pdf

²¹ ESFRI Roadmap 2018

<http://roadmap2018.esfri.eu/>

²² HLEG Report 2020

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/strategy_on_research_and_innovation/documents/ec_rtd_transfor_mative-impact-ris-on-euro-research.pdf

involve the decision to implement and fund the RI. Once realized, the RI enters the Operation Phase to produce frontier research and deliver advanced services for excellent science satisfying the users' demands.

Our analysis demonstrates that Core Facility Concept originates from the need of investigators to bring together and share cutting-edge research instruments that no-single laboratory might afford, nor fully exploit. As soon as the idea to bring together and share pre-existing high-quality equipment and specialized expertise is developed by the promoter Departments, a plan to update and maintain the collaborative resources is implemented and funded. At this stage, the CF is operational: it delivers research services and provides facilitated access to the common high-quality technological equipment. The decision to establish the Core Facility is taken at the university governance level upon proposal of interested Departments. Other Departments may decide to participate to the implementation of the CF as affiliated Departments in the implementation process (**Table 6**).

WEB	NET	PNIR	ACRONYM	NAME	TYPE	STRUCTURE	DEPARTMENTS NUMBER	START	PHASE
X	X	RI-R	CAAD	Centro di Ricerca Traslazionale sulle Malattie Autoimmuni e Allergiche	Research Centre	Inter-Departmental	4	2018	Operation
X	X	RI-R	CGS	Centro Grandi Strumenti	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental	11	2018	Operation
X	X	RI-R	CISUP	Centre for Instrument Sharing	Research Centre	Inter-Departmental	18	2018	Operation
X	X	RI-R	CPT	Centro Piattaforma Tecnologiche	Service Centre	Inter-Departmental	6	2015	Operation
X	X	RI-R	UNITECH NOLIMITS	NOvel Live biolmaging Milano cITà Studi	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental	14 plus one Centre	2015	Operation
X	X	RI-R	UNITECH OMICs	Metabolomics and lipidomics, Proteomics and Peptidomics	Research Platform	Inter-Departmental	10	2015	Operation
X	X		CAST	Center for Advanced Studies and Technology	Inter-Departmental	Service Centre			Not further analysed
X	X		CIBIO	Cellular, Computational and Integrative Biology	Intra-Departmental	Core Facility	1	2018	Operation
X	X		CRBA	Centro di Ricerca Biomedica Applicata	Inter-Departmental	Service Centre	5	2018	Operation
X	X		UNITECH CONSPECT	COmprehensive Substances characterization via advanced sPECTroscopy	Inter-Departmental	Research Platform	9	2015	Operation
X	X		UNITECH INDACO	INfrastruttura di Calcolo per Analisi di DATi COmplessi	Inter-Departmental	Research Platform	15	2015	Operation
X		RI-R	ATeN	Advanced Technologies Network Center	Inter-Departmental	Service Centre	Not indicated	2016	Operation
X		RI-R RI-N	CeTrA	Centre for Trace Analysis	Research Centre	Extra-Departmental	2 internal and 1 external		Preparation
X		RI-R	Polifab	Micro-fabrication Facility		Research Facility	2 plus one Foundation	2015	Operation
X		RI-R RI-N	STAR 2.0	Southern Europe Thomson Backscattering Source for Applied Research		Research Infrastructure		2011 2012 2016 2022*	Design Preparation Implementation Operation

Table 6. Number of affiliated Departments, establishment and lifecycle.

Most Case Studies were established in the last decade and are currently in the **Operation Phase**, delivering services to internal and, to a lesser extent, external users, academic organisations and private companies.

CF are initiatives with a highly dynamical early phase of establishment: the short lag between the Concept, the Implementation with the establishment and the Operation Phase is a hallmark of shared resources platform. Research Infrastructures, even in academic campuses, require substantially longer time for implementation. One example is the STAR 2.0 infrastructure at UniCal: its Design Phase started in 2011 and its Implementation Phase, that implies green-field construction of building and instruments – by means of PON funding²³ which supports projects aimed at the upgrading of 18 Research Infrastructures identified as priorities by the Ministry of University and Research in the PNIR 2014-2020 – is still running.

Mission, Vision and Values

Any initiative or organization shall have clear written *Mission*, *Vision* and *Values* statement. The *Mission* is a general statement about how to get to a specific destination by fulfilling a more prospective purpose to achieve, the *Vision*. In addition, *Core Values* represents the principles the leaders will follow in carrying out the activity of the organisation and are underpinning both *Mission* and *Vision*.

For effective communication, the *Vision* statement shall convey both the purpose and the values and describe the big picture of what the initiative wants to achieve (where we want to be, in the future); the *Mission* statement shall define both the purpose and the primary objectives and reflect every aspect of how the business will achieve that *Vision* (how you will get to where you want to be, now).

In Research Infrastructures, the *Vision* statement **communicates** the scientific rationale of the research conducted at the RI, its values and driving forces and how its relevance will impact on community; the *Mission* statement **defines** the scientific purpose and the primary goals related to user needs and team values. It may describe the range and nature of the products and services offered, pricing, quality, marketplace position, growth potential, use of technology, and relationships with stakeholders, users, employees, suppliers, competitors and community. Altogether, *Vision* and *Mission* define the wider ambition of a Research Infrastructure.

RIs are driven by specific scientific objectives and challenges and are designed to support scientists and technology developers whose frontier research projects are selected only by scientific merit. The establishment, development and operation of world-class research facilities of pan-European relevance addresses excellent science goals as well as the emerging challenges at European and global level. Provision of transnational access – by means of peer-review of competitive proposals – to unique and high-quality facilities, technologies, resources, expertise, innovative tools and services, is the common paradigm of RIs. This approach fosters collaboration between scientists from different countries, economic sectors, research fields, and organisations. It enhances innovation and technology development and can generate spin-off activities and new business, and overall socio-economic benefits.

²³ National Operational Programme on Research and Innovation 2014-2020
<http://www.ponricerca.gov.it/pon-ricerca/programme/>

The frame of the European Research Infrastructure missions have been extensively described in the ESFRI White Paper 2020: Making Science Happen – A New Ambition for Research Infrastructures in the European Research Area²⁴. The mission of a fully consolidated European ecosystem of Research Infrastructures is to underpin the new European Research Area (ERA), offering cross-disciplinary and integrated/harmonized R&D and innovation services, and enabling user communities both to pursue the greatest of scientific challenges and generate new knowledge, as well as to maximise their impacts on the most pressing of global societal challenges and the everyday life of European citizens. The joined science-driven and challenge-driven approach is particularly relevant for the Research Infrastructure contribution to the identified missions and partnerships under Horizon Europe²⁵.

While *Vision* and *Mission* of RIs are driven by a specific scientific objective or challenge addressed by European and international scientific communities (for an example, see **BOX 2** about EATRIS Statements), those of a Core Facility are focussed primarily on research resources, technological services and funding demands from academic researchers.

VISION

To make the translation of scientific discoveries into medical products more effective to improve human health and quality of life.

MISSION

To support researchers and the scientific community in developing their biomedical discoveries into novel translational tools and interventions for better health outcomes for society.

STRATEGY

To establish, develop and operate world-class research facilities for researchers in translational medicine.

GOAL

To bring together and provide access to a vast array of pre-clinical and clinical expertise and facilities for researchers in translational medicine, including clinician and healthcare systems.

Box 2. EATRIS Statements.

Our analysis shows that selected Core Facilities are driven by the technological research resources and financial needs and are specifically planned to support the researchers on campus and the scientific community to perform optimal design of studies and projects, delivering technology development and outstanding innovations. This *Vision* is achieved by managing and developing high-quality technological collaborative spaces and platforms that provide researchers with facilitated access to cost effective and state-of-the-art equipment, services and expert staff. These spaces are open to internal researchers and to some extent to external users, public or private. This approach foster the interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary research to promote its innovative potential and have an impact on research efficiency.

If the marketplace of Research Infrastructures is the broad new ERA, the arena of Core Facilities is more restricted to the local academic environment. The early nascent Italian Network of Core Facilities promoted by University of Trento is the first attempt at national level to demonstrate that fostering collaborative research across academic borders is critical for the implementation of a fully-consolidated ecosystem of Core Facilities at national level.

²⁴ ESFRI White Paper 2020: Making Science Happen – A New Ambition for Research Infrastructures in the European Research Area https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/White_paper_ESFRI-final.pdf

²⁵ Horizon Europe. Research and innovation funding programme 2021-2027. https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en

Strategies and Goals

Strategies and *Goals* are crucial elements to activate the *Mission* and achieve the *Vision* of any initiative. We have seen that *Strategy* at RIs is ‘to establish, develop and operate world-class research facilities of pan-European relevance’ by means of the primary *Goal* of ‘providing transnational access to unique and high-quality facilities, technologies, resources, expertise, innovative tools and services’.

By analogy, *Strategy* at CF is ‘to manage and develop high-quality technological collaborative spaces and platforms’ by means of the primary *Goal* of ‘pooling and sharing the most advanced technological resources to provide facilitated access to cost effective and state-of-the-art equipment, services and expert staff’.

A number of specific *Goals* and *Objectives* can be identified in the process of implementing the *Strategy* (Table 7).

	RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE	CORE FACILITY
DRIVE	Specific scientific question or challenge addressed by European and international scientific communities	Technological resources, technological services and finances demands from academic researchers
VISION	To find solutions to scientific questions to help tackling societal challenges	To provide shared resources to enhance academia commitment to research
MISSION	To support the scientific communities to perform frontier research to answer scientific questions and tackle emerging challenges that society is facing at European and global level	To support the researchers on campus to perform optimal design of studies and projects by fostering interdisciplinary research and cooperation among disciplines and sectors
STRATEGY	To establish, develop and operate world-class research facilities of pan-European relevance available to European scientists and to technology developers typically through peer review of competitive proposals	To manage and develop high-quality technological collaborative capabilities (spaces and human capital) accessible to researchers
GOALS	To coordinate and manage unique and high-quality facilities, technologies, resources, expertise, innovative tools and services To provide open access to a wide range of users, both from academia and industry across various research fields and sectors	To pool and share cost effective and state-of-the-art equipment, services and expert staff To facilitate access to a wide range of researchers from the public and private research and development sectors
OBJECTIVES	To increase the number of cutting-edge equipment, expertise and facilities To improve and optimise scientific development into effective innovative solutions To engage with public funding agencies, charities and policy makers with tailored actions to help improve the research and the innovation ecosystem To provide training and education and mentoring	To identify, implement and maintain high-quality services based on cutting-edge instrumentation To upgrade of the state-of-the-art equipment portfolio To select and instruct dedicated and high-qualified human resources To train laboratory managers and operators, including prospective personnel To facilitate access to a wide range of researchers from the public and private research and development sectors

Table 7. Vision and Mission, Strategy and Goal statements for Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities.

The analysis of Case Studies allow us to identify two main groups of Goals that help us better defining implementation steps of a Core Facility.

The *first pillar* of a Core Facility is related to the **management and development of high-quality technological collaborative capabilities**, including spaces, instrumentation and services (immobile resources) and human capital (mobile resources). Whether these capabilities are pre-existing the creation of the Core Facility or newly acquired, developed or exploited, a commitment must be in place to coordinate and expand them according to internal scientific needs.

Identification, implementation and maintenance of high-quality services based on cutting-edge instrumentation does run in parallel with the selection and exploitation of dedicated and high-qualified human resources that shall be trained and constantly updated.

The continuous upgrade of the state-of-the-art equipment portfolio, on one side, and the constant training of instrumentation managers and operators – including prospective personnel – that provide their expertise to interface with research investigators at diverse University Departments, on the other side, is the winning formula to foster frontier science at institutional level.

The *second pillar* is **fostering interdisciplinary research and cooperation with internal and external collaborators, including industry**. Core Facilities provide services and consultancy mostly to internal academic researchers but Cores' valuable equipment, scientific knowledge and technical guidance are aiming at being accessible to a wide range of researchers from the public and private research and development sectors.

The sharing of cutting-edge instrumentation and resources in common spaces, better if organised in advanced technology-based laboratories, pave the way to optimize the management of know-how and competences transversal to disciplinary research and R&D sectors and create collaborative workspace.

Indeed, Core Facilities represent collaboration platforms for users coming from diverse groups, fields and sector of research and development. Joint interdisciplinary collaboration fosters dialogue and exchanges between scientists from different disciplines, thus accelerating the maturation of novel ideas that are the source of scientific breakthroughs and shall have great technological impact.

In summary, most of the analysed Core Facilities indicated that they are providing cutting-edge technology and state-of-the-art instrumentation and services to a range of researchers, thus denoting the strong commitment of the University to scientific research. They declare to aggregate and merge technological resources and knowledge for which cost, operational investment, and expertise is most efficiently and effectively supported as shared resource. In other words, they provide high-quality services in terms of the most advanced instrumentation and qualified expertise that would not be otherwise available to any single researcher or group. In doing so, they are willing to promote interdisciplinary research, and foster scientific innovation and long-term sustainability at their own institution.

Thematic domains

Research Infrastructures can be clusterised in thematic domains according to the relevant scientific area of users' interests. ESFRI identified six domains, namely:

- DIGIT for Data, Computing & Digital Research Infrastructures
- ENE for Energy
- ENV for Environment
- H&F for Health & Food
- PSE for Physical Sciences & Engineering
- SCI for Social & Cultural Innovation

A number of sub-fields can be identified as well as areas of super-imposition and cross-disciplinarity.

Actually, although the Landscape Analysis performed by ESFRI is focussed on thematic area, ESFRI last Roadmap editions have entire section dedicated to the description of existing and potential interconnections among RIs within and across domains. This exercise has outlined in what science areas and in which forms the different RIs could work together, and which scientific needs and societal challenge can be addressed by stimulating scientific collaboration across different disciplines.

Cross-disciplinary research provides, indeed, a systemic mission-oriented approach towards achieving a specific goal. Such a model for designing and implementing research initiatives is increasingly adopted to exploit the capabilities and interests of the global research community, to work together towards an agreed and evidence-based set of end-points.

We have performed a thematic analysis on our Case Studies: first, we identified the specific objective(s) of the research operated at every laboratory/platform/unit identified within each Core Facility, and next, we classified them accordingly to the seven most represented categories of technological research operated:

	Micro-fabrication and nanotechnology facility
	Advanced Diagnostic Imaging
	Structural and compositional characterization of natural and synthetic materials
	Structural and functional characterization of inorganic and organic biomolecules
	Preclinical Model Organisms and Cell Biology
	Identification and quantification of DNA and RNA molecules
	Identification and quantification of molecules in different biological matrices

The following table summarises the results of the analysis (**Table 8**). The extended analysis is provided in **Annex 2**.

Case Studies can be classified as multi- or mono-thematic this last case when only a technology is in place to answer to specific users' demands. This occurs, for example, in Polifab which is dedicated to micro-fabrication and nanotechnology facility. Also UNITECHs are mono-thematic Platforms, each dedicated to a specific topic usually via a specific analytical technology. COSPECT focusses on 'Comprehensive Substances characterization via advanced Spectroscopy', NOLIMITS is centred on the 'Structural and functional biology of inorganic and organic molecules by means of *in vivo*, *ex vivo* and *in vitro* imaging', OMICs is targeted to 'Support proteomic, lipidomic and metabolomic studies based

on mass spectrometry', and INDACO is the meeting point for computational resources in term of processing and data storage for all the university community.

Table 8. Main objectives of the research al Laboratory/Platforms/Units and classification.

As regards the other Core Facilities, some are equipped with specific instruments and provide expertise critical for running research at biology-based Department such as CIBIO and CRBA, but also at CAAD that is a a disease-oriented research centre, both CF providing biotechnology resources for human health and medicine.

On the other way around, CISUP is more concentrated in developing large analytical instrumentations for Structural and compositional characterization of materials for nanotechnology and advanced technology.

ATeN, CPT and CGS are more transversal touching both Life Sciences and Materials Science with a special look at biomedical and pharmacological research.

In summary, our analysis demonstrates that Materials Science and Biological Sciences are the most common thematic area of application of services delivered by Core Facilities. Specifically, Core Facilities provide cutting-edge technology for research in Nanotechnology and Biotechnologies applied to health and medicine, pharmacology, agri-food and environment.

GOVERNANCE & MANAGEMENT

It is likely that the most reliable predictor of a Core Facility's success is operating with a clear mission driven by strong, effective leadership. The latter ideally includes a committed scientific director, experienced core director or manager, business administrator with experience in Core Facility support, engaged faculty advisory committee, and central oversight and support provided by a department, school, or center along with the Office for Research and/or Finance.

Each member of this leadership team shall contribute with a critical element of success, the technical experience, business know-how, research needs and vision, financial support, or help with regulatory compliance.

Structure, Responsibility and reporting lines

In general, the word 'Governance' means the set of structures, principles, rules, and procedures used to regulate the bodies – entities or organisms – that direct and control an organisation. 'Governance models' can be articulated on three parameters: i) the legal framework, ii) the governing bodies, iii) the competences on management. These set of rules are described in the *Statutes*, one of the most important documents that regulate an organization.

The Legal Framework

The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)²⁶ is the legal framework adopted by several European RIs. It has been designed to facilitate the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures of European interest with the involvement of several European countries. It complements national and inter-governmental schemes, providing a common legal framework based on Article 1872 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). At national level the most adopted legal models are: the Limited liability company, the CA Consortium Agreement, the Association (e.g. AISBL) and the Foundation.

In these type of legal framework shareholders are the Members States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC) whom representatives, usually the Ministry of Research, applied for being members. In doing so, an ERIC is a legal entity with legal personality and full legal capacity recognised in all EU Member States. Its basic internal structure is very flexible, leaving the members to define in the statutes, case by case, membership rights and obligations, the bodies of the ERIC and their competences. The liability of the ERIC's members will generally be limited to their respective contributions.

The analysed Core Facilities do not have a legal independency because operations for running the facility are regulated by specific *Rules and Guidelines* in the framework of University's laws and upon declaration and continuous update by Academic bodies. Nevertheless, an internal structure can be identified being the affiliated Departments the shareholders (members) of the initiative with rights and obligations, but importantly providing governing bodies with duties.

Governing Bodies and Structure

Despite the different legal framework adopted, every *Statutes* clearly indicates and describes *Governing bodies* and *structure* within the organization. In the *Statute* of an European RI, the main

²⁶ Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 of 25 June 2009 on the Community legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), OJ L 206, 8.8.2009, p. 1

Governing bodies are broadly reported as *General Assembly* and the *Director General* – Board of Directors in case of a collegiate body.

The *General Assembly* – also called Council, Board of Governors, Assembly of members – consists of one/two representatives from the government of each member country and shall provide the strategic and financial planning of the organization.

The *General Assembly*, as the body having ultimate decision-making authority, shall:

- define strategic and financial planning;
- adopt the work programme and budget;
- approve financial reports and the annual activity report;
- approve Agreements and Memorandums of Understanding with Members, and any rules, regulations, guidelines or other decisions required to ensure the performance;
- elect and dismiss the members of the Board of Directors and appoint the members of the other Committee;
- undertake any other functions conferred upon it by the Statutes, including by any annex or modifications hereto.

The *Director General* – also identified as *Executive Director*– is appointed by the *General Assembly* according to an open recruitment procedure defined by the General Assembly itself. The *Executive Director* shall select and appoint high level individuals to join the other members of the *Board of Directors* to:

- represent the legal entity;
- implement the General Assembly's directions and decisions, as well as the feedback from the other boards and committees;
- coordinate the day-to-day management.

Often this body is called *Executive Board* but the fact of being an executive does not preclude strategic management and coordination activities. Moreover, it must be recognized that most of the executive part of the Board's effort is entrusted to an efficient *Central Executive Management Office* that supports it, and a *Management Committee* that gives advice.

In addition to main Governing bodies, other boards and committees are established to provide support and strategic and scientific advice on several issues. The *Scientific Advisory Board*, for example, plays a major role for providing the Assembly of Member with strategic scientific advice, as well as the *Finance Committee* prepares opinions and recommendations on all financial matters.

A summary of the above mentioned bodies and duties for different type of RIs is given in **Table 9**.

GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE					
	DECISION	EXECUTIVE		OPERATION	
	decide on strategic orientations	coordinate day-by-day management		provide strategic and scientific advice	operate day-by-day
ERIC	Assembly of Members	Director General	Management Committee	Scientific and Ethical Advisory Board	Partner site
AISBL	General Assembly	Director General	Management Board	Coordination Council	Partner site
Consortium Agreement	Board	Directorate		Scientific Advisory Board	Partner site
Ltd	Council	Board of Directors			Partner site

Table 9. Governance Bodies in Research Infrastructures.

A schematic representation of a common *Governance Structure* that can be observed in an ERIC is given in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Diagramme model of an ERIC Governance Structure.

The analysis of the ‘*Rules and Guidelines*’ (General Regulation) document of the Core Facility Case Studies let us identify the Governance Bodies, Executive and Operation Profiles as listed in **Table 10**.

GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE				
	DECISION	EXECUTIVE		OPERATION
	decide on strategic orientations	coordinate day-by-day management	provide strategic and scientific advice	operate day-by-day
	ANNEX 3	ANNEX 4	ANNEX 5	ANNEX 5
				ANNEX 6
CAAD	Scientific & Technical Committee	Scientific Director	Administrative Manager	
CGS	Scientific & Technical Committee	Chair Research Support Area	Administrative Executive Manager	Lab Managers
CISUP	Centre Council	Director Board	Administrative Manager Technical Coordinator	Scientific Committee Lab Heads
CPT	Council	Director	Administrative Manager Technical Coordinator	Technical Scientific Committees Platform Managers
UNITECHs NOLIMITS	Scientific Committee	Scientific Coordinator Research Support Area (Unitech Office)	Technical Coordinator	Lab Managers
UNITECHs OMICS	Scientific Committee	Scientific Coordinator Research Support Area (Unitech Office)	Technical Coordinator	Lab Managers
CAST	NA			
CIBIO	Department Council	Core Facilities Delegate	Administrative Manager Core Facilities Coordinator	Core Facility Managers
CRBA	Council	Director	Administrative Manager Technical Coordinator	Lab Managers
UNITECH COSPECT	Scientific Committee	Scientific Coordinator Research Support Area (Unitech Office)	Technical Coordinator	Lab Managers
UNITECHs INDACO	Scientific Committee	Scientific Coordinator Research Support Area (Unitech Office)	Technical Coordinator	Lab Managers
ATeN	Council	Director	Administrative Manager Technical Manager Marketing Fundraising Manager	Area Managers Lab Managers
CeTrA	NA			
Polifab	Scientific Advisory Board	Scientific Director Research Support Area	Cleanroom Manager	External experts in the Scientific Advisory Board
STAR	Not in place			

Table 10. Governance Bodies in Core Facilities.

Analogies can be identified for decision-making, executive and operative levels of the process of running a Core Facility.

The decision-making body – who decides on strategic orientations of the Core Facility – is commonly named **Council** or **Scientific & Technical Committee** and consists of representatives identified among the academics of the affiliated Departments of the University. In only one case (i.e. CISUP) the Council is extended to all academics of the affiliated Departments and to any individual that requests to be admitted. On the contrary, at Polifab the Scientific Advisory Board comprises few internal Departmental representatives and some external advisors from public and private sectors (**Annex 3**). These decision-making bodies retain the following duties:

- define strategic and financial planning, in agreement with the strategic objectives established by the Academic Bodies;
- define the services and the activities;
- approve, within the budget, the general guidelines for the use of the financial resources;
- approve and periodically redefines the "Tariff and reimbursement plan" and the "Regulations for the use of spaces and equipment" taking into account the proposals from the Technical Coordinator;
- approve the annual activity report;
- approve the General Regulations;
- provide scientific support to the technical staff and users;
- can be consulted on any other relevant scientific topic.

The Council is represented by the **Director**, also named **Scientific Director** or **Scientific Coordinator**, who is commonly identified among the academics of the affiliated Departments and appointed by the Rector. A Deputy Director is often identified by the Director (**Annex 4**). A Director is responsible for the coordination of the day-to-day management and shall:

- represent the Center;
- convene and chair Council meetings;
- implement Council's decisions;
- supervise and coordinate activities;
- propose budget and financial plan;
- be responsible for spaces, services and resources;
- provide the annual activity report.

In the most advanced Case studies, the role of Executive Body – who is responsible for implementing Council decisions and coordinate day-by-day management – is shared with the Research Support Area (RSA). In this specific case, the organization has a dual line structure: the '*scientific line*' is led by the Scientific Coordinator and the '*administrative line*' is managed by the Research Support Area under which a dedicated **Administrative Manager** and a **Technical Coordinator** are identified (e.g. CGS, UNITECHs and Polifab) Sometimes the two roles are merged within one profile that day-by-day manages activities to run the facility (see for example the Administrative Executive Manager in CGS, **Annex 5**).

Specifically, the **Administrative Manager** or RSA Office is responsible to:

- manage the human resources;

- prepare the budget according to the revenues and in line with the decisions of the Scientific Committee
- check the sustainability of financial plans;
- submits to the Academic bodies, in collaboration with the Technical Coordinator, an annual report on the performance.

The **Technical Coordinator** shall:

- organise and coordinate the activities;
- manage technological resources;
- coordinates staff personnel activities;
- supervise the service access;
- suggest the plan for service rates and the general guidelines for users;
- prepare the annual activity report.

Operative bodies in Core Facilities are **Lab or Platform Managers** that operate day-by-day, they:

- collaborate with the Coordinator in managing the rooms, the instrumentation and research progression
- provide widespread scientific support to the researchers

More details on competences and duties profiles are given in **Annex 6**.

Management and Organisation

The comprehensive analysis of the above competences profile gives the description and the diagramme representation for the management and organization of Case Studies as provided in the following.

The **CAAD** is managed by the **Scientific Director** and the **Scientific and Technical Committee** represented by the affiliated University Departments and Research Structures and associated external centres/entities. The administrative management is provided by UPO central administration which identifies the **Administrative Manager (Figure 5)**.

Figure 5. Diagramme model of CAAD Governance Structure.

The **CGS** is managed by the **Scientific Director** and the **Scientific and Technical Committee** – represented by the affiliated University Departments – and the General Administration represented by the **Research and Third Mission Area** under which the **Administrative Executive Manager** is identified. The Centre is organized in Laboratories each coordinated by a **Lab Manager** (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6. Diagramme model of CGS Governance Structure.

The **CISUP** is managed by the **Director**, with the support of the **Board**, made of a representation of the **Council**, which consists of academics from the affiliated University Departments and technical staff assigned to the Centre. Researchers from external structures and technical staff of other Departments of UniPi can support CISUP activity as CISUP’s fellows. The operative management is represented by the **Administrative Manager** and the **Technical Coordinator**. Additionally, the Director – with the support of the Board – can appoint a **Scientific Committee** to give scientific advice and recommendation (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Diagramme model of CISUP Governance Structure.

The **CPT** is managed by the **Director** and the **Council** – represented by the affiliated University Departments – with the support of the **Administrative Manager** and the **Technical Coordinator**. Each platform is supervised by one or two **Platform Managers**, whom in collaboration with some reference professors, ensure that the scientific aims are fulfilled. Additionally, the Director – with the support of

the Council – can appoint a **Technical Scientific Committee (TCS)** for each Platform to give scientific advice and recommendation (**Figure 8**).

Figure 8. Diagramme model of CPT Governance Structure.

Each **UNITECHs** is managed by the **Scientific Coordinator** and the **Scientific Committee** made of representative of UniMI Departments. The organization has a dual line structure: the ‘scientific line’ is led by the **Scientific Coordinator** and the ‘administrative line’ is managed by the **Research Support Area** under which the **Unitech Office** and the **Technical Coordinator** are identified (**Figure 9**).

Figure 9. Diagramme model of UNITECHs Governance Structure.

The **CIBIO Core Facilities** are managed by the **Department Council** through the **Core Facilities Delegate** (Director’s nominee), with the support of an **Administrative Manager** and the **Core Facilities Coordinator**. The Core Facilities are organized into thematic research areas, which are organized and supervised by Core Facility Managers. The CF Managers collaborate with the CF Coordinator in managing the rooms, the instrumentation and research progression, with widespread support to the researchers (**Figure 10**).

Figure 10. Diagramme model of CIBIO CF Governance Structure.

The **CRBA** is managed by the **Director** and the **Council**, a representative of the affiliated Departments, with the support of the **Administrative Manager** and the **Technical Coordinator**. The Centre is divided into thematic research areas named laboratories, which are organized and supervised by **Lab Managers**. The Lab Managers collaborate with the Coordinator in managing the rooms, the instrumentation and research progression, with widespread support to the researchers (**Figure 11**).

Figure 11. Diagramme model of CRBA Governance Structure.

The **AteN** Centre is managed by the **Director** and the **Council** – represented by the affiliated University Departments – with the support of the **Administrative Manager** for the administrative issues, the **Marketing and Fundraising Manager** for the implementation and exploitation of outcomes and the **Technical Manager** who is responsible for running the Facility. The Facility is organized in Macroareas – each represented by an academic –, and each Macroarea comprises pertinent laboratories – each coordinated by a **Laboratory Manager** (**Figure 12**).

Figure 12. Diagramme model of ATeN Governance Structure.

The **Polifab** is managed by the **Scientific Director** and the **Scientific Advisory Board** made of representative of PoliMi Departments and external advisors. The organization has a dual line structure: the ‘scientific line’ is led by the **Scientific Director** and the ‘administrative line’ is managed by the **Research Support Area** under which a **Cleanroom Manager** is identified (**Figure 13**).

Figure 13. Diagramme model of Polifab Governance Structure.

The most peculiar case is represented by Polifab for several reasons. We list here some of the features that shall be implemented in a working model for Core Facilities.

1. The *Scientific Advisory Board* – the decision-making body – is composed of a small number (five) of internal representatives from Politecnico Departments appointed by the Academic Senate and identified by the Rector on proposals of involved Departments and (two) external advisors (also from the private sector) appointed by the Academic Senate, identified and proposed by the Scientific Board.

In most of the other CFs, the decision-making body is composed of few representatives of the affiliated Department(s) with the exception of CISUP where individuals may apply to be member of the Council, also from external entities.

2. The *Director* – the executive body – is appointed by the Scientific Board among its members (three-year term with renewal).

In most of the other CFs, the Director is appointed by the Rector among professors of the Council with the exception of UNITECHs where the Scientific Coordinator is appointed by the Scientific Committee among its members (three-year term with renewal).

3. The *Executive management* has a dual line structure and reporting lines: the ‘scientific line’ is led by the **Scientific Director** and the ‘administrative line’ is managed by the **Research Support Area (RSA)** under which the **RSA Office (Delegate)** and the **Cleanroom Manager** are identified. The Research Support Area Office is provided by the Research Support Area while the Cleanroom manager is appointed by the Head of the Research Support Area upon Director’s consultation.

The organizational structure is shared with CGS and UNITECHs where the Unitech Office is provided by the Research Management Sector of the Research Support Area and the Technical Coordinator is identified by the Scientific Committee and appointed by the General Director.

In the other cases, the organization is more flat having the Director in charge of managing the implementation of the Council’s decisions by means of the support provided by few administrative and technical profiles directly appointed by the university General Director.

Human resources management

A Human resources policy must be in place to guarantee the necessary competences for operation, users programme, education and training by equal opportunity hiring and secondments.

Human resources include technical and administrative staff. Core Facilities shall provide qualified and specialized technical personnel, experienced both in the use and maintenance of the instrumental resources available on the platform, and in the provision of research support services. The platform can promote and finance the training and updating of related technical and administrative staff. The need for human resources and the relative forms of recruitment are assessed, on the basis of the specific needs identified, by the Research Services Area in agreement with the Scientific Committee, also on the proposal of the Technical Coordinator.

Higher roles and responsibilities are attributed to academic professors belonging to the involved Departments. Staff personnel, including the Technical Coordinator and the Lab Managers, is generally appointed by the General Director among enrolled personnel with proven experience in the field. Most of the cases shows that a common practice is to second technicians and technologists according to their involvement in research groups or research projects embedded in the facility. Some CFs may benefit from the collaboration of personnel made available by public and private bodies, as well as external personnel assigned in the context of specific training and research projects.

Only in two cases (i.e. AteN and CIBIO) technical staff personnel is selected by competitive calls open to internal professors and researchers (AteN) and also to external candidates (CIBIO).

For details see **ANNEX 6**.

ACCESS PROGRAMME

Access, Users and Tariffs

The analysed Core Facilities provide open-access to pay-per-use services. Reservation to access to the facility is frequently made through an online system according to the level of autonomy in operations. Different levels may be identified as in the case of CPT (see **BOX 3**).

Level 1: autonomous use. Trained users can use the facility instrumentation by themselves. The technicians manage the booking, ensure the proper equipment functioning and the access to laboratory rooms. The technicians ensure also that the users are aware of the laboratory safety measures.

Level 2: supervised use. The users need support by CPT staff to use the machines. The technicians train users to use the equipment by themselves.

Level 3: full service. The users need assistance by technicians in different phases of experiment (design, set-up, data acquisition, data analysis and interpretation). This level require a project feasibility evaluation, the CPT Director approval and a CD ratification.

Box 3. Level of autonomy of users accessing the CPT facilities.

Users are internal and external researchers, from public and private enterprises (**Table 11**). There is a sort of priority list to access facilities and services which is given to internal academic users over external users, either public or private. No selection based on a merit peer-review is usually undertaken according to the “first come, first served” rule. A feasibility evaluation may be provided.

Internal member from University Departments

Internal from University Departments

External users from public research bodies and public administrations

External users from private entities

Table 11. User type accessing Core Facilities.

Service prices are determined on the basis of users’ typology: if internal, applied rates are lower than that for external users – non-profit and for-profit – and according to specific and public tariffs (**Table 12**). Tariffs may be fixed rates or based on an hourly basic fee and have additional cost if without or with assistance of a technical operator depending on level of user’s autonomy.

Service prices according to the University's internal rates

Service prices according to the University's external not-for-profit rates

Service prices according to the University's external for-profit rates

Table 12. Services rates at Core Facilities.

The UNITECHs, but also CPT and CRBA, represent peculiar cases given that the affiliated Departments are also ‘subscriber’ Departments and pay an annual fee for the Platform development. UNITECH’s users from ‘Subscriber’ Departments access the facilities at even lower price (see **ANNEX 7**).

Data Policy

A clear policy on data is not reported, except in CISUP's 'Guidelines for the operations of the instruments' where we can read that "people responsible for running the facility shall [...] provide a Data Management Plan of the experiments, in particular the structuring of the data according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

RESOURCES AND FUNDING

Material, human and economic resources

Resources of a Core Facility can be material, human and economic.

Material resources are represented by instrumental assets managed by the platform for the performance of its business. These resources can be:

- conferred by the University research structures or Departments;
- acquired by the platform itself within the limits of the assigned budget;
- conferred in various capacities by companies, foundations, public bodies or other private entities on the basis of specific agreements and conventions.

Human resources include technical and administrative staff (see above). Core Facilities provide qualified and specialized technical personnel, experienced both in the use and maintenance of the instrumental resources available on the platform, and in the provision of research support services. The platform can promote and finance the training and updating of related technical and administrative staff. The need for human resources and the relative forms of recruitment are assessed, on the basis of the specific needs identified, by the Research Services Department in agreement with the Scientific Committee, also on the proposal of the Technical Manager.

Financial resources can be either coming from internal or external contributions and incomes as detailed in the following **Table 13**.

INTERNAL

University contribution (budget)

Incomes from service rates, reimbursements and contributions (internal users)

Internal funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CF

free contribution

EXTERNAL

Incomes from service rates, contracts and agreements with third parties (public and private bodies) for activities of research and consultancy

External funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CF

free contribution

Table 13. Financial resources at Core Facilities.

For in depth analysis see **ANNEX 8**.

Investments opportunities and funding

The budget allocated to Research Infrastructures under the National Research Infrastructure Plan 2021-2027 increased in time compared to the previous programmes, with a current capability of € 1.08 billion allocated between 2021 and 2027 to finance at least 20 Research Infrastructures.

It is therefore clear that the PNIR alone will not be sufficient to deliver against the ambitions of an evolving ecosystem of Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities. Such investments will only occur if a better interplay between international, EU and national and regional funding is in place.

A number of the analysed Core Facilities has already been identified as priority investments at regional, national and European level and been awarded with grants by applying to competitive calls with proposals for the implementation of Research Infrastructures under EU-funded programmes. As an example, the Regional Operational Programme (ROP) under the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)²⁷ provides investment funds with the priority objectives of the Region's economic growth and social development as well as the enhancement of its productive capabilities. A tentative list of funding measures is provided in **Table 14** along with previous fundings received at national and European level²⁸. A more detailed analysis is undergoing.

REGION	UNIVERSITY	PNIR	ACRONYM	REGIONAL FUNDING	NATIONAL FUNDING	EUROPEAN FUNDING
PIEMONTE	UniPO	RI-R	CAAD	Regione Piemonte. Regional Operational Programme (ROP) under the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) 2014-2020		
LOMBARDIA	UniPV	RI-R	CGS			
TOSCANA	UniPI	RI-R	CISUP			
VENETO	UniVR	RI-R	CPT		Funds for university buildings and large scientific equipment (MUR Decree 1274)	
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	RI-R	UNITECH NOLIMITS			
LOMBARDIA	UniMI	RI-R	UNITECH OMICs			
ABRUZZO	UniCH		CAST			
PA TRENTO	UniTN		CIBIO	Provincia Autonoma di Trento. Regional Operational Programme (ROP) under the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) 2014-2020		
EMILIA-ROMAGNA	UniBO		CRBA			

²⁷ European Regional Development Fund
https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/funding/erdf/

²⁸ National Operational Programme on Research and Innovation
https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/atlas/programmes/2014-2020/italy/2014it16m2op005

LOMBARDIA	UniMI		UNITECH COSPECT	
LOMBARDIA	UniMI		UNITECH INDACO	
SICILIA	UniPA	RI-R	ATeN	Regione Sicilia-Misura 4.1.2.PON R&C, Infrastrutture (Progetto PONa3_00273) e del PO FESR
VENETO	UniVE	RI-R RI-N	CeTrA	
LOMBARDIA	PoliMI	RI-R	PoliFAB	
CALABRIA	UniCAL	RI-R RI-N	STAR 2.0	Regione Piemonte. Regional Operational Programme (ROP) under the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) 2014-2020 National Operational Program Research 2007- 2013. National Operational Programme (NOP) 2014- 2020

Table 14. Investments in Core Facilities.

CONCLUSIONS

Our analysis shows the following recurring features for selected university-set Core Facilities.

- Are **organised as ‘Service Centre’ or ‘Research Platform’** thus underlying their commitment to **provide shared resources and services to support research**. Their structure is most frequently interdepartmental and intramural being promoted by several Departments within the same university.
- Are driven by the technological research resources and financial needs and **are specifically planned to support the researchers on campus and the scientific community** to perform optimal design of studies and projects, delivering technology development and outstanding innovations.
- Are managing and developing **high-quality technological collaborative spaces and platforms** that provide researchers with facilitated access to cost effective and state-of-the-art equipment, services and expert staff. These spaces are open to internal researchers and to some extent to external users, public or private. This approach foster the interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary research to promote its innovative potential and have an impact on research efficiency.
- Were established in the last decade and are currently in the **Operation Phase**, delivering services to internal and, to a lesser extent, external users, academic organisations and private companies.
- Can be **multi- or mono-thematic**, depending on the range of technology in place to answer to widespread users’ scientific demands. Materials Science and Biological Sciences are the most common thematic area of application of services. Specifically, Core Facilities provide cutting-edge technology for research in **Nanotechnology** and **Biotechnologies applied to health and medicine, pharmacology, agri-food and environment**.
- Do not have a legal independency because are set in the framework of University’s laws. Nevertheless, an **internal organizational and managerial autonomy**, in compliance with the University regulations for administration, finance and accounting, is structured with **clear governing bodies and reporting lines**.
- The **decision-making body** – who decides on strategic orientations of the Core Facility – is commonly named **Council** or **Scientific & Technical Committee** and consists of representatives identified among the academics of the affiliated Departments of the University. The Council is represented by the **Director**, also named **Scientific Director** or **Scientific Coordinator**, who is commonly identified among the academics of the affiliated Departments and appointed by the Rector.
- The role of **Executive Body** – who is responsible for implementing Council decisions and coordinate day-by-day management – is covered by the Director and sometimes shared with the **Research Support Area (RSA)**. In this specific case, the organization has a dual line structure: the *‘scientific line’* is led by the Scientific Coordinator and the *‘administrative line’* is managed by the Research Support Area under which a dedicated **Administrative Manager** and a **Technical Coordinator** are identified.

- **Human resources** include technical and administrative staff. Core Facilities provide qualified and specialized technical personnel, experienced both in the use and maintenance of the instrumental resources available on the platform, and in the provision of research support services. Staff personnel, including the Technical Coordinator and the Lab Managers, is generally appointed by the General Director among enrolled personnel with proven experience in the field. A common practice is to second technicians and technologists according to their involvement in research groups or research projects embedded in the facility.
- **Provide open-access to pay-per-use services.** Reservation to access to the facility is frequently made through an online system according to the level of autonomy in operations. Users are internal and external researchers, from public and private enterprises. There is a sort of priority list to access facilities and services which is given to internal academic users over external users, either public or private. No selection based on a merit peer-review is usually undertaken according to the “first come, first served” rule.
- **Service prices are determined on the basis of users’ typology:** if internal, applied rates are lower than that for external users – non-profit and for-profit – and according to specific and public tariffs. Tariffs may be fixed rates or based on an hourly basic fee and have additional cost if without or with assistance of a technical operator depending on level of user’s autonomy.
- In addition to material (e.g. equipment, instruments, consumables) and human (staff personnel) resources, also **Financial resources** are accounted from internal or external contributions, incomes from service rates, contracts and agreements with third parties (public and private bodies) for activities of research and consultancy. Some resources are derived from participation to competitive projects with resources assigned to CF.
- **Investment opportunities** have already being investigated by Core Facilities and successfully undertaken at regional, national and European level. A more detailed analysis of the participation of Core facilities at funded projects is undergoing.

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1

Departments affiliated to Core Facilities, in alphabetical order.

ACRONYM	STRUCTURE	DEPARTMENTS	START	PHASE
CAAD	Inter-Departmental	Dipartimento di Medicina Traslazionale Dipartimento di Scienze del Farmaco Dipartimento di Scienze della Salute Dipartimento di Scienze e Innovazione Tecnologica	2016	Operation
CGS	Inter-Departmental	Dipartimento di Biologia e Biotecnologie Dipartimento di Chimica Dipartimento di Fisica Dipartimento di Ingegneria Industriale e dell'Informazione Dipartimento di Medicina Interna e Terapia Medica Dipartimento di Medicina Molecolare Dipartimento di Sanità Pubblica, Medicina Sperimentale e Forense Dipartimento di Scienze Clinico Chirurgiche, Diagnostiche e Pediatriche Dipartimento di Scienze del Farmaco Dipartimento di Scienze del Sistema Nervoso e del Comportamento Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra e dell'Ambiente	2018	Operation
CISUP	Inter-Departmental	CISUP gathers 477 faculty members and technical staff from 18 UniPI Departments	2018	Operation
CPT	Inter-Departmental	Dipartimento di Diagnostica e Sanità Pubblica Dipartimento di Medicina Dipartimento di Neuroscienze, Biomedicina e Movimento Dipartimento di Scienze Chirurgiche, Odontostomatologiche e Materno Infantili Dipartimento di Informatica Dipartimento di Biotecnologie	2015	Operation
UNITECH NOLIMITS	Inter-Departmental	Dipartimento di Bioscienze (DBS, leader) Dipartimento di Biotecnologie Mediche e Medicina Traslazionale (BIOMETRA) Dipartimento di Chimica Dipartimento di Fisica Dipartimento di Medicina Veterinaria e Scienze Animali (DIVAS) Dipartimento di Oncologia (DIPO) Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie ed Ambientale (DISAA) Dipartimento di Scienze Biomediche Chirurgiche e Odontoiatriche (DSBCO) Dipartimento di Scienze Biomediche per la Salute (SCIBIS) Dipartimento di Scienze della Salute (DISS) Dipartimento di Scienze e Politiche Ambientali (DESP) Dipartimento di Scienze Farmacologiche e Biomolecolari (DISFEB) Dipartimento di Scienze per gli Alimenti, la Nutrizione e l'Ambiente (DEFENS) Dipartimento Scienze Farmaceutiche (DISFARM) Centro di Ricerca Pediatrica Romeo ed Enrica Invernizzi	2015	Operation
UNITECH OMICS	Inter- Departmental	Dipartimento di Scienze Farmacologiche e Biomolecolari (DISFEB, leader) Dipartimento di Bioscienze (DBS) Dipartimento di Biotecnologie Mediche e Medicina Traslazionale (BIOMETRA) Dipartimento di Fisiopatologia Medico-Chirurgica e dei Trapianti (DEPT) Dipartimento di Medicina Veterinaria e Scienze Animali (DIVAS) Dipartimento di Scienze Biomediche e Cliniche (DIBIC) Dipartimento di Scienze Biomediche per la Salute (SCIBIS) Dipartimento di Scienze Cliniche e di Comunità (DISCCO) Dipartimento di Scienze della Salute (DISS) Dipartimento di Scienze Farmaceutiche (DISFARM)	2015	Operation
CAST	Inter-Departmental	Dipartimento di Medicina e Scienze dell'Invecchiamento Dipartimento di Scienze Mediche, Orali e Biotecnologiche Dipartimento di Neuroscienze, Imaging e Scienze Cliniche Dipartimento di Scienze Psicologiche, della Salute e del Territorio	2015	Operation
CIBIO	Departmental	Cellular, Computational and Integrative Biology (CIBIO)	2018	Operation

CRBA	Inter-Departmental	Dipartimento di Medicina Specialistica, Diagnostica e Sperimentale (DIMES, leader) Dipartimento di Scienze Mediche e Chirurgiche (DIMEC, leader) Farmacia e Biotecnologie (FaBiT) Scienze Biomediche e Neuromotorie (DIBINEM) Scienze per la Qualità della Vita (QUVI)	2018	Operation
UNITECH COSPECT	Inter-Departmental	Dipartimento di Chimica (leader) Dipartimento di Bioscienze (DBS) Dipartimento di Biotecnologie Mediche e Medicina Traslazionale (BIOMETRA) Dipartimento di Medicina Veterinaria e Scienze Animali (DIVAS) Dipartimento di Scienze Biomediche per la Salute (SCIBIS) Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra (DST) Dipartimento di Scienze e Politiche Ambientali (DESP) Dipartimento di Scienze Farmaceutiche (DISFARM) Dipartimento di Scienze per gli Alimenti, la Nutrizione e l'Ambiente (DEFENS)	2015	Operation
UNITECH INDACO	Inter-Departmental	Dipartimento di Fisica (Leader) Dipartimento di Bioscienze (DBS) Dipartimento di Chimica Dipartimento di Economia, Management e Metodi Quantitativi (DEMM) Dipartimento di Fisiopatologia Medico-Chirurgica e dei Trapianti (DEPT) Dipartimento di Matematica Dipartimento di Medicina Veterinaria e Scienze Animali (DIVAS) Dipartimento di Oncologia ed Emato-Oncologia (DIPO) Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie e Ambientali (DISAA) Dipartimento di Scienze Biomediche e Cliniche (DIBIC) Dipartimento di Scienze Cliniche e Comunità (DISCCO) Dipartimento di Scienze della terra (DST) Dipartimento di Scienze e Politiche Ambientali (DEPS) Dipartimento di Scienze Farmaceutiche (DISFARM) Dipartimento di Scienze Farmacologiche e Biomolecolari (DISFEB)	2015	Operation
ATeN	Inter-Departmental	Not indicated	2016	Operation
CeTrA	Extra-Departmental			Preparation
Polifab	Inter-Departmental	Department of Electronics, Information and Bioengineering Department of Physics CIFE Foundation	2015	Operation
STAR 2.0			2011 2012 2016 2022*	Design Preparation Implementation Operation

Annex 1. Affiliated Departments to Core Facilities.

ANNEX 2

Main objectives of the research al Laboratory/Platforms/Units and classification.

ACRONYM	MACROAREA	LABORATORY/PLATFORM/UNIT	SCIENTIFIC OBJECTIVE							
CAAD	Translational Research on Advanced Microscopy (AM) Autoimmune and Allergic Diseases	Structural and molecular organization of both live/fixed cells and tissues, and time-lapse investigations								
		Bioinformatics (BINF)	Support designing, conducting and interpreting high-throughput experiments biology							
		BSL3 (B3)	Biosafety Level 3 (BSL3) Biocontainment Facility							
		Genomics & Transcriptomics (GT)	High-throughput genomic and transcriptomic experiments for biomarker discovery and/or analyses of multifactorial and monogenic traits							
		In Vivo Imaging (IVI) in SPF animal facility								
		Meta/Genomics/Proteomics (META)	Identification of the quality and quantity of the microorganisms present in an environment (microbiota) through the analysis of their genomes (microbiome) and transcriptomes (meta-transcriptomics)							
		Metabolomics & Proteomics (MP)	Comprehensive analyses of proteins, small molecules and lipids from different matrices							
		Next-Generation Flow Cytometry & Sorting (NGCS)	Simultaneous measurement of up to 29 different antigens of a single cell							
		Protein Technologies (PT)								
		UPO-Biobank								
CGS	Biotechnology applied to human health and materials science	Confocal Microscopy	Structural and functional characterisation of biological structure (DNA and DNA-protein complexes, cytoskeleton microtubules, neurofilaments, organelles, etc.) by means of <i>in vivo</i> , <i>ex vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> imaging							
		Cristallography and X-Ray Diffractometry (XRD)	X-ray diffraction study of the atomic structure of crystalline solids							
		Cryo-Electron Microscopy	Structural characterisation of biological macromolecules (proteins, nucleic acids and their complexes) at near-atomic resolution.							
		Cytofluorimetry	Qualitative and quantitative measure of heterogeneous cell suspensions or particles							
		Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and micro-Computed Microtomography (μCT)	Morphologic, metabolic and functional information from organs and tissues							
		Mass Spectrometry	To identify unknown compounds, to quantify known compounds and to elucidate the structure and chemical properties of molecules							
		Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR)	Structural and dynamical characterisation of inorganic and organic samples							
		Primary structure of protein	Amino acid analysis and N-terminal sequencing							
		Scientific prototyping								
		Spectroscopy	Analysis of the structural properties of biomolecules and optically active compounds as well as the determination of the secondary structure of proteins and conformational variations.							
		Transmission Electron Microscopy TEM	Perform observation of biological specimens							
		CISUP		Additive Manufacturing Service	Nanomaterials, processes and devices					
Calorimetry Service	Structural and compositional characterization of natural and synthetic materials									

	Deposition Service	Nanomaterials, processes and devices	
	Electrophysiological & neuroimaging techniques Service	Advanced Diagnostic Imaging	
	High-content imaging system Service	Structural and functional characterization of inorganic and organic biomolecules by means of <i>in vivo</i> , <i>ex vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> imaging	
	Imaging Service	Structural and functional characterization of inorganic and organic biomolecules by means of <i>in vivo</i> , <i>ex vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> imaging	
	LINAC (Linear Accelerator) Service	Advanced Diagnostic Imaging	
	Mass Spectrometry Service	Structural and compositional characterization of natural and synthetic materials	
	Material Analysis Service	Structural and compositional characterization of natural and synthetic materials	
	Microscopy Service	Structural and functional characterization of inorganic and organic biomolecules by means of <i>in vivo</i> , <i>ex vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> imaging	
	Nanolayering Service	Nanomaterials, processes and devices	
	Nuclear Magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy Service	Structural and compositional characterization of natural and synthetic materials	
	Ultrasound Service	Advanced Diagnostic Imaging	
	X-Ray Diffraction Service	Structural and compositional characterization of natural and synthetic materials	
CPT	Spectroscopy, Diffractometry and molecular interaction study Platform	Characterisation of organic and inorganic molecules, macromolecules and their interaction by means of spectroscopy, diffractometry and molecular interaction study platform	
	Imaging Platform	Structural and functional characterization of subcellular structures and organisms by means of <i>in vivo</i> , <i>ex vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> imaging	
	Flow cytometry and cellular analysis Platform	Functional characterisation of biological multiples profiles (proteins, epitopes, nucleic acids, ion concentration, high content) in a single cell, in a very high number of cells (high throughput)	
	Genomics and transcriptomics Platform	Analysis of the transcriptome and the genome of microorganisms, animal plants and humans	
	Mass Spectrometry Platform	Identification, characterisation and quantification and measurement of elements, compounds and macromolecules	
	Computational Platform	Analysis of complex data by provision of dedicated computing power and data storage	
UNITECH NOLIMITS	<i>in vivo</i> , <i>ex vivo</i> and <i>in vitro</i> imaging	Structural and functional characterization of subcellular structures and organisms	
UNITECH OMICS	Mass Spectrometry	Identification and quantification of molecules in different biological matrices and plant extracts based on	
CAST	NA		
CIBIO	Biotechnologies for human health	Advance Molecular Diagnostic (CIBIO-DMA)	
	Advanced Imaging (AI)	Structural and functional characterization of subcellular structures and organisms	
	Bioinformatics	Support to computational analysis	
	Cell Analysis and Separation	Cell analysis and sorting	

	Bioimaging and dosimetry	Exploring the structure, dynamics and function of fluorescent molecules in different environments				
	Classical and Advanced Spectroscopy	Structural and functional characterization of molecular systems, as well as simple and complex material systems (organic, biological, hybrid)				
	Surfaces, Thin Films and Devices	Preparation and / or modification of solid surfaces and for their characterization				
CeTrA	NA					
Polifab	Clean Room	Proof-of-concepts on materials, processes and devices, as well as a fast prototyping of innovative devices				
STAR 2.0						

Annex 2. Main objectives of the research al Laboratory/Platforms/Units and classification

ANNEX 3

Decision-making bodies in Core Facilities: decide on strategic orientations.

		DECISION	
		WHO	WHAT
CAAD	Scientific & Technical Committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific Director - two academic representatives from each affiliated Departments - one representative from affiliated external centre/entity - Rector or his/her delegate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - define the strategic planning - approve the multiannual activity and development plan, upon Director's proposal - approve, within the budget, the general guidelines for the use of the funds - approve the annual activity report - approve the General Regulation and amendments - agrees on affiliation of members - approve agreements and contracts with third parties
CGS	Scientific & Technical Committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chair - one academic representative from each affiliated Department - Research and Third mission Area Director (or delegate) - Administrative Executive Manager - one representative of the technical-administrative staff personnel of the Centre (experts) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - approve the annual planning of activity and development - approve, within the budget, the general guidelines for the use of the funds, resources and spaces - approve the annual activity report - approve agreements, contracts and tariffs for third parties - approve the General Regulations
CISUP	Centre Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Director and deputy Director - academics affiliated to CISUP - technical staff assigned to CISUP - representatives of students at different levels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - define the planning and development of the activities - approve, within the budget, the general guidelines for the use of the funds, resources and spaces, including staff and equipment - approve agreements, contracts and tariffs for third parties - approve the financial planning - approve the General Regulation - plan the scientific activity - approve the annual activity report
CPT	Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Director - Rector (or Delegate) - one representative professor from each affiliated Department 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - identify strategic and development lines - approve the annual plan for activity, costs and budget - approve, within the budget, the general guidelines for the use of the funds, resources and spaces - approve strategic and financial planning - decide on activities, spaces and services - decide on access requests and tariffs - approve the annual activity report - approve the General Guidelines and suggestions of revision
UNITECH	Scientific Committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific Coordinator - one representative from each 'subscriber' Departments - Research Support Area Head or delegate - Technical Coordinator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - define the services and the activities of the Platform, its planning and development, in agreement with the strategic objectives established by the Academic Bodies - approve, within the budget, the general guidelines for the use of the funds - approve and periodically redefines the "Tariff and reimbursement plan" to be proposed to the Board of administration and the "Regulations for the use of spaces and equipment" taking into account the proposals from the Technical Coordinator - approve the General Regulations of the Platform - provide scientific support to the Technical Coordinator and Platform users - can be consulted on any other topic relevant to the Platform

CAST	Centre Steering Committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Director and deputy Director - Seven academics from affiliated Departments and appointed by CdA 	-
CIBIO	Department Council		
CRBA	Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Director - Rector delegate - up to 12 professors and researchers from promoter/participant Departments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 professors and/or researchers from DIMEC and DIMES • 2 professors and/or researchers from DIBINEM • 1 professor and/or researchers from FaBiT and QUVi - 5 representatives from IRCCS UniBO - Administrative Manager - Technical Coordinator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - approve the general guidelines for the use of the resources - provide the budget to the Academic bodies - approve the financial plan - decide on activities, spaces and services - decide on access requests and tariffs - approve the annual activity report - approve the General Regulations
ATeN	Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Director - one academic representative from each affiliated Department - one academic representative for each Macroarea - one representative for Lab Managers - Technical Manager - Administrative Manager - Marketing and Fundraising Manager - Pro-Rector for Research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - identify strategic and development lines - establish the general rules for the use of the allocated funds and instrumental resources - approve the annual plan for activity, costs and budget - approve the internal Guidelines for operations - decide on activities, spaces and services - decide on access requests and tariffs - agree on contracts with public and private entities - annually establishes the rates for the use of equipment for occasional services by public and private bodies - approve the budget proposal to be submitted to the Central Administration - approve the annual activity report - approve the organizational structure - identify laboratory managers - undertake any other functions conferred upon it by the Regulation
CeTrA	NA	-	-
Polifab	Scientific Advisory Board	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - five internal professors (appointed by the Academic Senate and identified by the Rector on proposals of involved Departments) - max two external members (appointed by the Academic Senate and identified by the Scientific Board) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - define the strategic and development planning - evaluate the annual activity and results, identifying resources needed to achieve the strategic objectives - approve the agreements with external bodies to be submitted to the governing bodies - propose the "Tariff and reimbursement plan" to be submitted to the University Consiglio di Amministrazione - approve, on Scientific Director proposal, the proposal of budget to be submitted to the Head of Research Support Area (RSA) - submit proposals for needs of spaces and personnel staff to the Head of Research Support Area (RSA)
STAR		Not in place	

Annex 3. Decision-making bodies in Core Facilities.

ANNEX 4

Decision-making/Executive bodies in Core Facilities: coordinate day-by-day management making proposals and implementing decisions.

		DECISION/EXECUTIVE	
		WHO	WHAT
CAAD	Scientific Director	Appointed by the Rector upon Technical & Scientific Committee proposal (four-year term with two renewals)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - participate to TSC meetings - propose the strategic and financial plan - implement TSC decisions - prepare the annual activity report
	Chair	Appointed among professors by the Rector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - represent the Center - convene and chair Council meetings
CGS	Deputy Chair	Appointed by the Chair among professors of the affiliated Departments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - define the strategic and development lines - propose the strategic and financial plan, in concert with the Research Area Director and the Administrative Executive Manager - prepare the annual activity report
	Director	Appointed by the Rector among professors of the Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - represent the Center - convene and chair Council and Board meetings, acting as a moderator for discussions
CISUP	Deputy Director	Appointed by the Director among professors of the Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - propose the annual activity report - manage the spaces and the services - coordinate the technical and administrative staff - manage the budget and moreover, with the support of the Board - propose, within the budget, the annual planning of the activities - propose, within the budget, the financial planning for running the Centre, including equipment maintenance and new acquisition - promote collaboration for financing - plan services rates according to users' categories - prepare the financial report
	Board	mandated by the Council, consists of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Director - Deputy Director - eight Council academics - Administrative Manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - support the Director in implementing Council's decisions
	Director	Appointed by the Rector upon Council's proposal (three-year term with renewal)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - represent the Center - convene and chair Council meetings - suggest the strategic and development lines - propose the annual activity plan, including the budget - prepare the annual activity report - supervise the activities - be liable for spaces, services and resources - be responsible for security - agree on contracts with public and private entities
UNITECH	Scientific Coordinator	Appointed by the Scientific Committee among its members (three-year term with renewal)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - chair the Scientific Committee meetings - propose the budget and resources requests, in concert with the Technical Coordinator and the Unitech Office - supervise the implementation of The Scientific Committee's decisions - coordinate and supervise the activities - responsible for spaces, services and resources, human and technical
CAST	Director	Appointed by the Rector under CdA's proposal among Steering Committee (three-year term with renewal) Appointed by the Director among Steering Committee's members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -
CIBIO	Core Facilities Delegate		

CRBA	Director	Appointed by the Council among its academic members (three-year term with renewal)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - represent the Center - convene and chair Council meetings - implement Council's decisions
	Deputy Director	Appointed by the Director among Council's members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supervise and coordinate activities - propose budget and financial plan - responsible for spaces, services and resources - provide the annual activity report
ATeN	Director	Appointed by the Rector among professors and permanent researchers of the University (three-year term with renewal)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - represent the Center - convene and chair Council meetings - implement Council's decisions
	Deputy Director	Appointed by the Director among the member of the Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supervise and coordinate the activities, including the identification of responsibilities - propose the annual activity plan, including the budget - prepare the annual activity report - responsible for spaces, services and resources
CeTrA	NA		-
Polifab	Scientific Director	Appointed by the Scientific Board among its members (three-year term with renewal)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - represent Polifab - convene and Chair the Scientific Board meetings - oversees the implementation of the strategies and development plan defined by the Scientific Board
	Deputy Director	Appointed by the Scientific Director among the members of the Scientific Board	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - approve communication of activities - evaluate the projects and approve their realisation together with the assessment of the financial plan - establish agreements with external bodies and submits them for approval by the Scientific Committee - submit any proposals for revision of the regulation to the Scientific Board - approve the cost proposals submitted by the Head of Services (or RSA Delegates) to the Head of the Research Support Area
STAR	Scientific Coordinator	ongoing	

Annex 4. Executive bodies in Core Facilities.

ANNEX 5

Executive/Administrative bodies in Core Facilities: manage day-by-day to implement decisions and operate the facility.

		EXECUTIVE/ADMINISTRATIVE	
		WHO	WHAT
CAAD	Administrative Manager	Appointed by the University General Director	- manage the financial resources according to UPO guidelines and regulation
CGS	Administrative Executive Manager	Appointed by the University General Director among technical-administrative personnel upon proposal of the Chair and the Research and Third Mission Area Director	- coordinate the technical staff personnel, in line with decisions of the Scientific and Technical Committee - supervise operations - prepare the budget, according to the revenues and in line with the decisions of the Scientific Committee - manage spaces and resources - supervise the service access - suggest the plan for service rates, the guidelines and the General Regulations
CISUP	Administrative Manager	Appointed by the Council	- ensure the performance of the administrative and accounting activities, in agreement and jointly with the Director - manage the financial resources with the procedures of the University Administration, Finance and Accounting Regulations - provide the assessment of income, the assumption of commitments, the liquidation of expenses, as well as the signing of the accounting documents - archive official and accounting documents
	Technical Coordinator		- ensure the operational activities upon Director's recommendation and mandate - manage the organizational issues
	ADVISORY Scientific Committee	Mandated by the Council, consist of: - a coordinator from the Council - 3 to 6 members appointed by the Director among high-level international experts	- express an opinion on the results obtained by the Center in the previous year, in relation to future programs and projects and scientific and financial planning - suggest any improvement or supplementary / development actions to be taken
CPT	Administrative Manager		
	Technical Coordinator	Appointed by the General Director among technical staff personnel with proven experience in the field	- coordinate and manage spaces and services - coordinate technical, human and financial resources - suggest the plan for equipment maintenance - implement Council's decisions
	ADVISORY Technical Scientific Committees	Mandated by the Council, consist of: - Director - Academia representatives (not in the Council and with proven methodological, managerial and scientific competence) - Technical-administrative representatives with proven skills and competence in managing equipment - Executive Coordinator - Platform Managers	- provide scientific support to the Executive Coordinator and Platform users - advise and support on any other topic relevant to the Platform
UNITECH	Unitech Office	Provided by the Research Management Sector of the Research Support Area	- manage the human resources - check the sustainability of financial plans - prepare the budget according to the revenues and in line with the decisions of the Scientific Committee - submit to the Academic Senate and the Board of Directors, in collaboration with the Technical Coordinator, an annual report on the performance

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - convene the ordinary meetings of the Scientific Committee and the extraordinary meetings, upon proposal of the Scientific Coordinator or of a third of the members of the Scientific Committee
	Technical Coordinator	Appointed by the General Director, identified by the Scientific Committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organise and coordinate the activities - manage technological resources - coordinates staff personnel activities - supervise the service access - suggest to the Scientific Committee, in concert with the UNITECH Office, the plan for service rates and the general guidelines for users - prepare the annual activity report
CAST	NA		-
CIBIO	Administrative Manager	Appointed by the CIBIO Director among technical-administrative staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - manage the financial resources according to CIBIO guidelines and regulation
	Core Facilities Coordinator	Appointed by the CIBIO Director among technical-administrative staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supervise the structure, spaces, resources and personnel
CRBA	Administrative Manager		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - assists the Director to ensure the management of administrative, financial and accounting activities - control of the acts and procedures adopted
	Technical Coordinator		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - maintain the efficiency of the laboratory with a view to integration, optimization and rationalization of resources - organise access to services, use of spaces and equipment - guarantee safety procedures
ATeN	Administrative Manager	Appointed by the University General Director	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensure the performance of the administrative and accounting activities, in agreement and jointly with the Director - manage the financial resources with the procedures of the University Administration, Finance and Accounting Regulations - provide the assessment of income, the assumption of commitments, the liquidation of expenses, as well as the signing of the accounting documents - archive official and accounting documents
	Technical Manager	Identified among graduated technical personnel, is appointed by the University General Director	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensure the operational activities upon Director's recommendation and mandate - manage the organizational issues - in charge of the safety, prepare the ordinary and extraordinary maintenance plan for the equipment
	Marketing and Fundraising Manager	Appointed by the University General Director	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - coordinate the marketing plan to donor and public audiences including creating and managing operational plans
CeTrA	NA		-
Polifab	Research Support Area Office	Provided by the Research Support Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - approve the administrative and managerial procedures - defines the schedule of the activities on the basis of the commitments undertaken by the Laboratory
	Cleanroom manager	Appointed by the Head of the Research Support Area (RSA), on Director's consultation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - manage human and material resources, coordinating activities, assigning operational tasks to personnel, defining the programming of human and material resources - responsible for compliance with workplace safety regulations - identifies staff training needs - verifies and ensures the adequacy of personnel qualifications and related documentation - assesses any need for materials / equipment for carrying out the activities, reporting them to the Scientific Director - defines and approves the activity sheet with the project owners

STAR	- responsible for the commitments undertaken by the Laboratory with the clients, in terms of timing and correct management of the activities
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Annex 5. Executive/Administrative bodies in Core Facilities.

ANNEX 6

Operative bodies in Core Facilities: operate day-by-day.

		OPERATIVE	
		WHO	WHAT
CAAD		No clear indication of profiles and responsibilities	
CGS	Laboratory Managers	Appointed by the General Director	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organize, coordinate and manage the lab activities - prepare a detailed lab activity report for the Executive Manager
CISUP	Lab Heads	No clear indication of profiles and responsibilities	
CPT	Platform Managers	Appointed by the General Director	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - collaborate with the Coordinator in managing the rooms, the instrumentation and research progression, with widespread support to the researchers
UNITECHs	Lab Managers	No clear indication of profiles and responsibilities	
CAST	NA		
CIBIO	Core Facility Managers	Selected by the CIBIO Director by competitive calls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - collaborate with the Coordinator in managing the rooms, the instrumentation and research progression - widespread scientific support to the researchers
CRBA	Lab Managers	No clear indication of profiles and responsibilities	
ATeN	Area Managers	Appointed by the Rector upon Director's proposal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - represent the laboratories belonging to the macroarea - coordinate and supervise macroarea activities
	Laboratory Managers	Selected by the Council by competitive calls open to professors and researchers from UniPA (two-year term with renewals)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organize, coordinate and manage the lab activities - prepare a detailed lab activity report for the Council - provide information about safety and risk to the Technical Manager
Polifab	Process Specialists	No clear indication of profiles and responsibilities	
CeTrA	NA		
STAR			

Annex 6. Operative bodies in Core Facilities.

ANNEX 7

Analysis of the users' typology and the access mode.

ACRONYM	USERS	TARIFFS	ACCESS
CAAD	Internal from UniPO Departments	Service prices according to the University's intramural rates	The CAAD is open to all users according to booking agenda and service complexity. Booking is managed by online platform (AGENDO).
	External from public or private	Service prices according to the University's extramural rates	
CGS	Internal from UniPV Departments	Service prices according to the University's internal rates	Access to the platform is guaranteed to all University researchers with priority over external users by booking online services and according to specific users tariffs
	External from public or private	Service prices according to University's external rates	
CISUP	Internal member from UniPI Departments	Service prices according to the University's internal rates (A)	Priority to all internal University users over external users, academic and non-academic, and managed by booking online services, according to specific users fees and tariffs.
	Internal from UniPI Departments	Service prices according to the University's internal rates (B)	
	External users from public research bodies and public administrations	Service prices according to the University's external rates for non-profit bodies (C)	
	External users from private entities	Service prices according to the University's external rates (D)	
CPT	Internal from UniVR Departments	Service prices according to the University's internal rates (A)	The CPT is open to internal and external users with priority given to internals over externals. Reservation to access to facility is made through an online system according to the level of autonomy in operations.
	External users from public research bodies and public administrations	Service prices according to the University's external non-for-profit rates (B)	
	External users from private entities	Service prices according to the University's external for-profit rates (C)	
UNITECHs The Subscriber Departments pay an annual fee for UNITECH development	Internal from Subscriber UniMI Departments	Service prices according to the University's internal rates (A)	Priority to all University research structures over external users, academic and non-academic, and managed by booking online services, according to specific users subscription fees and tariffs
	Internal from Non-subscriber UniMI Departments	Service prices according to the University's internal rates (B)	
	External from public research bodies and public administrations	Service prices according to the University's external not-for-profit rates (C)	
	External from private entities	Service prices according to the University's external for-profit rates (D)	
CAST	NA		
CIBIO	Internal from UniTN Departments	Service prices according to the University's internal rates (A)	Priority to all internal University research structures over external users, academic and non-academic, and managed by booking online services, according to specific users service tariffs.
	External from public research bodies and public administrations	Service prices according to the University's external rates (B)	

	External from private entities	Service prices according to the University's external rates (C)	
CRBA	Internal from affiliated University Departments and Hospital Units	Service prices according to the University's internal rates (A)	Project submission and feasibility assessment by the Board, economic contribution calculation according to the Service Chart.
	Internal from other University Departments	Service prices according to the University's internal rates (B)	
	Some users may be external public or private		
ATeN	Internal from UniPA Departments and research structures	Service prices according to the University's internal rates (A) The internal users pay a contribution according to a quotation that includes reimbursement for full consumable costs and staff activities including the use and ordinary maintenance of equipment (determined on the basis of the standard hourly cost of a researcher, equal to 31 euros)	The ATeN is open to internal and external users with priority given to internals over externals. Requests for services are managed through the on-line booking system. The Administrative Manager, the Technical Manager and the Laboratory Manager receive a report to assess the nature of the activity that the applicant intends to carry out.
	External from public research bodies and public administrations, private entities	Service prices according to the University's external rates	Requests for collaboration in specific projects of high relevance must be forwarded to the Director of the Center who recommends them for approval to the Center Council. The access and use of the laboratory equipment is allowed to the technical staff of the Center or to subjects previously authorized by the Director after obtaining the opinion of the Technical Manager.
CeTrA	NA		
Polifab	Internal from PoliMi Departments	Payment of each access to the cleanroom and to the various facilities, according to the price per hour of each machine. Flat rate contracts, allowing for the use of most of the facilities and consumables (substrates and expensive materials excluded), according to the general regulation on the machine booking, with a flat rate payment connected to the presence of a single operator in the cleanroom during a defined period of time (12 months, full and half scheme); Services, according to R&D contracts. Work performed by Polifab staff.	Polifab is an open-access, pay-per-use facility. All new cleanroom users must first attend a safety course and obtain a Polifab safety course certificate before access to the cleanroom is granted. A specific training on the machines of interest is then required, under the guidance of the technical staff of Polifab. The users must pass a test before they are allowed to directly use the machines, according to a general regulation on the booking and use of the facilities. Shared access to cleanroom facilities is regulated by a booking system available in the Polifab intranet.
	External from institutions (no-profit) and industries (profit)		
STAR 2.0			

Annex 7. Users and access mode at Core Facilities.

ANNEX 8

Analysis of the financial resources.

ACRONYM	FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT	INTERNAL RESOURCES	EXTERNAL RESOURCES
CAAD	The CAAD administration is governed by the Regulations of the University for administration, finance and accounting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University contribution (budget) <hr/> - income from services provided at established rates to internal users <hr/> - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - income from services provided at established rates to external users <hr/> - other contribution from public administrations <hr/> - other contribution from private entities <hr/> - free contribution
CGS	The CGS has organizational and managerial autonomy in compliance with the University regulations for administration, finance and accounting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University contribution (budget) <hr/> - Department contributions (additional) <hr/> - Incomes from service rates, reimbursements and contributions (internal users) <hr/> - internal calls for projects with resources assigned to CGS <hr/> - free contribution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incomes from service rates, contracts and agreements with third parties (public and private bodies) for activities of research and consultancy <hr/> - external calls for projects with resources assigned to CGS <hr/> - free contribution
CISUP	The CISUP has organizational and managerial autonomy in compliance with the University regulations for administration, finance and accounting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University contribution (budget) <hr/> - Incomes from service rates, reimbursements and contributions (internal users) <hr/> - Internal funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CISUP <hr/> - free contribution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incomes from service rates, contracts and agreements with third parties (public and private bodies) for activities of research and consultancy <hr/> - external funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CISUP <hr/> - free contribution
CPT	The CPT has organizational and managerial autonomy in compliance with the University regulations for administration, finance and accounting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equipment <i>5-6 M € (2016-2018)</i> <hr/> - Annual University contribution <i>Fondo di Finanziamento Ordinario (FFO): 300.000 €/year</i> <hr/> - Annual Subscribers' Departments fee <i>Annual fee/platform: 1.500 €</i> <i>Overhead: 0.8% project funding</i> <hr/> - Other Department contributions <hr/> - Incomes from service rates, reimbursements and contributions (internal users) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incomes from service rates, contracts and agreements with third parties (public and private bodies) for activities of research and consultancy

		- Internal funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CPT <i>e.g. PNRR on RI (BMRR, MIRRI)</i> <i>e.g. Funds for university buildings and large scientific equipment (MUR Decree 1274)</i>	- external funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CPT <i>e.g. Fondazione CariVerona</i>
UNITECHS	The UNITECHs have organizational and managerial autonomy in compliance with the University regulations for administration, finance and accounting	- Equipment	
		- University contribution (budget)	
		- Annual Subscribers' Departments fee	
		- Incomes from service rates, reimbursements and contributions (internal users)	- Incomes from service rates, contracts and agreements with third parties (public and private bodies) for activities of research and consultancy
		- Internal funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to UNITECH	- external funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to UNITECH
		- free contribution	- free contribution
CAST	NA		
CIBIO	The CIBIO administration is governed by the Regulations of the University for administration, finance and accounting	- Annual University contribution (budget)	
		- Incomes from service rates, reimbursements and contributions (internal users)	- Incomes from service rates, contracts and agreements with third parties (public and private bodies) for activities of research and consultancy
		- Internal funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CIBIO	- external funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CIBIO
		- free contribution	- free contribution
CRBA	The CRBA has organizational and managerial autonomy in compliance with the University regulations for administration, finance and accounting	- Operating Fund (Fondo di Funzionamento). Contributions from promoter/participating Departments + all S. Orsola IRCCS Units to cover costs for running the Centre and including technical, logistic and administrative services, equipment maintenance, reagents and commonly used laboratory material, quality certification	
	Development Fund (Fondo di Sviluppo) to cover costs for developing the Centre and including:	- Incomes from service rates, reimbursements and contributions (internal users)	- Incomes from service rates, contracts and agreements with third parties (public and private bodies) for activities of research and consultancy

		- Internal funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CIBIO	- external funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to CIBIO
		- free contribution	- free contribution
ATeN		- Annual University contribution (budget)	-
		- Incomes from service rates, reimbursements and contributions (internal users)	- Incomes from service rates, contracts and agreements with third parties (public and private bodies) for activities of research and consultancy
		- Internal funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to ATeN	- external funds for competitive projects with resources assigned to ATeN
		- free contribution	- free contribution
CeTrA	NA		
Polifab	NA		
STAR 2.0	NA		

Annex 8. Financial resources at Core Facilities.